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The effects of external electric fields on proteins

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Proteins are highly abundant and, as a biomolecular class, have very versatile functions in living systems. Protein structure contains electrically charged residues and proteins electrostatics is crucial for their function. Although protein activity is commonly modulated through variety of ligands and post-translational modifications, external electric field (EF) represents an alternative, physical approach. By exerting forces on charged and dipolar regions, EFs can reshape the energetic landscape and dynamic behavior of proteins. This approach offers a mass-free, rapidly switchable, spatially precise, non-contact, and reagent-free way to control protein conformation and function – features increasingly appealing for applications in green bioprocessing, neuromodulation, ultrafast structural biology, and in studying proteins without clearly ligandable sites. Despite the growing evidence for diverse and reversible control of proteins by EF, the mechanisms are still underexplored and applications have not yet grown to their full potential. This review focuses on molecular mechanisms and integrates the findings of the effects of external EFs on proteins from both computational simulations and experimental studies. The literature shows that EF acts on protein charged and dipolar groups, and when the EF parameters are well tailored, EF consequently triggers effects on protein rigid body motion, secondary, tertiary structure, quaternary structure and molecular conformation, ultimately leading to changes in protein interactions and function (enzymatic, ion channelling, switching, ...). These effects are being utilized not only on proteins as food components but also for bionanotechnological applications, e.g. in membrane proteins for controlling their transport properties, in structural and force-generating proteins to steer self-assembly pathways and dynamic behavior. The compiled evidence clarifies key mechanisms by which EFs influence proteins and identifies promising directions for biomedical, food-processing, and biotechnological applications.

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1	Introduction	5	2
2	Mechanisms of EF action and effects on proteins	6	3
2.1	Effects on protein rigid body motions	7	4
2.1.1	Translational (linear) motion	7	5
2.1.2	Rotational motion	7	6
2.2	Effects on protein structure	9	7
2.2.1	Effects on conformation and tertiary structure	9	8
2.2.2	Effects on secondary structure and unfolding	11	9
2.3	Effects on energetic and thermodynamic properties	12	10
2.3.1	Free energy landscape	12	11
2.3.2	Crystallization	14	12
2.4	Effects on electrostatic, mechanical and dynamic properties	15	13
2.4.1	Effective electric charge and dipole, local electrostatic environment	15	14
2.4.2	Nanomechanics of proteins	16	15
2.5	Effects on protein interactions	17	16
2.5.1	Protein-protein interactions: quaternary structure, multimeric complexes, fibrils and polymers	17	17
2.5.2	Effects on protein - ligand binding	19	19
2.6	Effects on additional protein functions	20	20
2.6.1	Enzymatic function	20	21
2.6.2	Membrane proteins function	21	22
2.6.3	Photonic/luminescence functional properties	22	23
3	Indirect effects of EF exposure	22	24
3.1	Indirect electrophysical effects of EF	23	25
3.1.1	Heat generation	23	26
3.1.2	Heat and EF induced flows	23	27
3.1.3	Shockwaves	24	28
3.2	Indirect electrochemical effects of EF	24	29
3.2.1	pH change	24	30
3.2.2	Reactive species generation	25	31
3.2.3	Bubble formation	25	32
4	Discussion	25	33
4.1	EF strength and timescale: their scaling and (mis)match between simulations and experiments	25	34
4.2	Solvent- and ion-mediated contributions: bridging direct and indirect effects	28	36
4.3	Research at higher complexity scales: protein-containing biosystems and biosamples	29	37
4.4	Further outstanding questions for future research	30	38
4.4.1	How does protein structure affects the protein susceptibility to EF ?	30	39

40	4.4.2 What is the reversibility of the EF effects on proteins ?	31
41	5 Conclusion	32

Accounting for roughly half of the dry mass of most metabolically active cells^{1,2}, proteins form the single largest class of macromolecules, and play a key role, such as catalysis, regulation, and spatiotemporal organisation, in biological systems. At a cellular level, the vast majority of structural aspects and main functions of the human body and all kingdoms of life are carried out by proteins³.

Function of proteins is determined by its primary sequence and the explicit conformation of the polypeptide chain⁴. Accordingly, the structure, conformational dynamics, and function of proteins and their assemblies⁵, as well as strategies to modulate them^{6,7}, have been the focus of considerable research attention. Anomalies in these protein systems result in serious disruptions of cellular function and give rise to a variety of diseases^{8–10}. For example, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases are proteinopathies associated with protein misfolding and subsequent amyloid formation¹¹. Although protein malfunction underlies many pathological conditions, properly functioning proteins act as highly efficient molecular machines – both *in vivo* (for example, flagellar motors, myosin, DNA and RNA polymerases) and in bionanotechnological applications: serving as nanomotors¹², nanoscissors (lytic and cleavage enzymes)¹³, nanoassembly lines (synthase enzymes)¹⁴, and photo-electric transducers (light-harvesting protein complexes)¹⁵.

Therefore, having the ability to control the protein structure and conformation, hence protein function, using electric field (EF), as possible in other molecules^{16–19}, is a formidable opportunity for the development of methods in biotechnology, structural biology, physical chemistry, nanotechnology, biosensing, analytics, food industry and medicine, which have features unattainable by and complementary to chemical control only^{7,20}. External EFs offer a fundamentally *mass-free, energy-only, parallel* handle on proteins: EF delivers force to every copy of the macromolecule without adding reagents, avoiding the stoichiometric constraints, toxicity, and downstream purification inherent to ligand or covalent chemistries: an advantage already exploited in pulsed EF (PEF) bioprocessing, where sub-millisecond bursts reshape proteins in aqueous media with no added solvent²¹. Voltage control also translates into *electronic speed*: nanosecond EF of ≈ 100 MV/m have driven Å-scale conformational transitions that can be imaged in real time by electric-field-stimulated X-ray crystallography, a timescale orders of magnitude faster than ligand binding or covalent chemistry²². Crucially, the stimulus can be *delivered entirely without contact*: picosecond PEF radiated from dielectric-rod or wide-band antennas have been shown to trigger cellular responses without electrodes²³ and microwave and THz EF bursts drive conformational changes in enzymes or disassemble non-covalent protein polymers^{24,25} and even modulate cellular activity²⁶. Because EFs couple to charge and permanent or induced dipoles rather than to a defined binding pocket, they can bias catalytic and allosteric energy landscapes even in “undruggable” proteins. This review surveys recent studies on how external EF (pulsed, static, and oscillating up to the low-THz range) influence protein structure, conformation, and function, both in isolated molecules and in assemblies.

Why can EFs influence and potentially control protein function? Typically, proteins are charged dielectric nano-objects with a complex multipolar charge distribution^{27–31}. Consequently, the protein electrostatics (the distribution and interaction of electric charges within a protein) is a critical feature influencing its structure, stability, and function^{32–34}. Strong molecular EFs are known to play an essential role in protein folding³³, protein-ligand³⁵, protein-solvent^{32,36}, protein-protein³⁷ interactions,

84 molecular recognition³⁸, as well as enzyme catalysis^{39–42}. Some proteins' conformation is naturally
85 regulated by EFs *in vivo*: voltage-gated ion channels switch between open and closed states depending
86 on the voltage across the membranes in which they are incorporated^{43–45}. For these reasons, it is rea-
87 sonable to assume that external EFs with appropriately chosen parameters of EF strength, waveform
88 and spatial structure could modulate protein function or be used to probe the biophysical properties
89 of proteins.

90 Our major focus is on works that provide a mechanistic (protein structure and dynamics-based)
91 understanding of the observed effects so that the electromagnetic-field-based control of protein func-
92 tion and geometry can be rationally developed for the benefit of biomedicine and bionanotechnology,
93 exemplified by our recent works^{21,46,47}. While there are reviews which cover some selected form of EF
94 on proteins or application focus, they lack the comprehensive focus on mechanisms and often include
95 complex samples (emphasizing food products or protein extraction from tissues^{48–63}, or focusing on
96 protein structures in cells^{64,65}) which prevents drawing mechanistic conclusions about the EF effects
97 on proteins.

98 The structure of our paper is as follows: after an introduction, we move step-wise from fundamen-
99 tal mechanisms of EF action on proteins, covering effects on protein motion, structure, energetics,
100 electrostatics, interactions, and function. We provide detailed comprehensive tables of experimental
101 (Table 2) and computational works (Table 3), with necessary methodical parameters, focusing on pure
102 or well-defined protein samples. We include sections on indirect electrophysical and electrochemical
103 influences, and conclude by addressing outstanding challenges, and outlining future research direc-
104 tions.

105 2 Mechanisms of EF action and effects on proteins

106 At the length and energy scales of chemistry and biology, every force (direct or emergent from many
107 body interactions) that holds atoms together inside a molecule (covalent, ionic) or brings separate
108 molecules together (hydrogen bonds, electrostatic, van der Waals, ...) in solution is ultimately a
109 manifestation of the electromagnetic interaction⁶⁶. Many non-covalent molecular interactions are a
110 direct consequence of electrostatic and (quantum) electrodynamic interactions⁶⁷. Therefore, the EF
111 naturally has a supreme position in the understanding of and action on the behavior of atoms and
112 molecules. The interaction of an EF with matter fundamentally arises from its coupling to electric
113 charges (ionic or electronic). In proteins, the direct interaction with an external field occurs due to
114 the presence of electric charges on specific ionizable groups (fixed charges) of the constituent amino
115 acids. Examples include glutamic acid and aspartic acid, which carry negative charges, and lysine,
116 arginine, and histidine, which carry positive charges. The ionization state and the actual electric
117 charge of these groups depend on the pH of the environment. The mechanistic molecular dynamics
118 simulation study demonstrated on a model peptides⁶⁸ that the effect of EF on a peptide (namely on
119 Root-mean-square deviation of the peptide) is proportional not to the net charge of a protein, but to
120 number of charged residues, directly confirming the role of charged residues presences in EF effects
121 on proteins.

122 Furthermore, an EF can interact with mobile electrons, such as the delocalized π -electrons found
123 in amino acids such as tryptophan, tyrosine, and phenylalanine. The EF \vec{E} exerts a force $\vec{F} = q \cdot \vec{E}$
124 on electric charge q . As a result, the atomic groups with zero net charge or dipole are unaffected

directly by the EF. It can be helpful to visualize the charged groups in a protein as the points where the EF exerts its influence. However, even non-charged groups may be affected indirectly. This occurs through interactions mediated by the surrounding solvent, nearby charged groups, or even distant charged groups within the protein structure.

The characteristics of an EF can vary based on its temporal and spatial parameters, which significantly influence its effects on proteins. Key parameters include the EF's vector (magnitude and direction), spectral (temporal) content and spatial distribution. The EF can be modulated in time in various ways, delivered as a complex waveform, or applied as a train of pulses, among other variations. For example, when the EF is delivered in pulses (Pulsed Electric Field - PEF)⁶⁹, the number of pulses and the intervals between them (determined by an inverse parameter known as the firing frequency) are crucial factors. Each of these parameters can influence how the EF interacts with individual protein molecules or protein assemblies. Beyond temporal structuring, the electromagnetic field can also be spatially shaped⁷⁰⁻⁷². However, creating complex EF spatial patterns, particularly at molecular scales and in three dimensions, presents significant technical challenges. Such efforts approach the physical limits of current nanotechnology⁷³⁻⁷⁵ and photonics and have therefore not been extensively explored for protein control. Here a great portion of inspiration can be absorbed from nature, as the biomolecular interactions are largely enabled by the fact that the biomolecules including proteins themselves are nanoscale devices generating spatial complex EF^{34,76} with dynamic range across 12 orders of magnitude in time⁷⁷ and Å spatial precision.

2.1 Effects on protein rigid body motions

2.1.1 Translational (linear) motion

The simplest effect of an EF on a protein structure with non-zero electric charge is the linear (translation) motion caused by electric force. This effect is exploited in a wide family of electrophoresis-based liquid or gel analytical techniques covered in a plethora of review articles and books, e.g.^{83,84}. On the level of larger protein assemblies, both linear and rotational motion induced by EF (static or oscillating) was observed and exploited for characterization and micromanipulation of single microtubules and their networks. This has been done either by dielectrophoretic effects using an alternating EF (frequencies up to 10 MHz)⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷ or long electric pulses (tens of seconds to minutes) using a static EF (direct current)⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰, and often in combination with kinesin-coated surfaces that power the MTs' motion^{85,89,91,92}. Similarly, but in fewer works, the EF has been used for the manipulation of actin filaments⁹³⁻⁹⁶.

These works demonstrate that EF can act on protein polymer fibers, leading to their linear and turning motions, hence enabling molecular manipulation at the single protein fiber level. Those results have a potential significance for bio-nanotechnological manipulation techniques and provide inspiration for what effects one could expect on the single protein level.

2.1.2 Rotational motion

Rigid-body rotational degrees of freedom (in which whole domains pivot as nearly rigid units about hinge axes) give proteins a low-energy mechanism to re-orient catalytic or binding surfaces, synchronize multi-step reaction cycles, and transmit long-range allosteric signals, thereby serving as a fundamental determinant of protein function⁹⁷⁻¹⁰². Hence, EF has the potential to influence and

165 manipulate a variety of these rotation-dependent functions.

166 The tendency of a protein dipole moment to turn and align with an EF is the core physical princi-
167 ple of EF mediated protein rotation and is also in the essence of a wide-spread dielectric spectroscopy
168 techniques, in which the relaxation of the real part of the permittivity of the proteins solutions is
169 intrinsically related to protein rotational diffusion^{103,104}. The rotation of proteins by EF has been also
170 observed using optical methods, by analyzing the anisotropy of the optical signal, which is caused by
171 EF-induced rotation of proteins, as illustrated in Figure 2^{81,105–117}. However, the EF turning effects
172 on proteins are poorly experimentally investigated at the single protein level. The two major reasons
173 are (i) the difficulty to observe or image a single protein orientation on short time scales and (ii)
174 high EF strength might be required to overcome the rotational diffusion due to thermal motion. So
175 far, there have only been a few computational works that have demonstrated this effect, see Table 3,
176 which may guide future experiments along these lines. An emerging area where rotational manipula-
177 tion of proteins with EFs would have a large impact is X-ray imaging of single molecules⁷⁹. In X-ray
178 Single Particle Imaging (SPI), individual proteins are injected with random orientation into vacuum
179 where they are exposed to the extremely intense (up to 10^{12} photons per pulse), femtosecond pulse
180 delivered by the XFEL, each giving rise to a diffraction pattern reflecting its orientation at the time
181 of exposure¹¹⁸. From the diffraction data the three-dimensional (3D) structures of the proteins can
182 in principle be determined, alleviating the need for crystallization or other limitations that restrict
183 conventional techniques for structural biology. Powerful algorithms¹¹⁹ exist to assemble the data and
184 enable structure determination, but they can be stumped by sparse or missing data, or noise from ra-
185 diation damage¹²⁰, electronics or sample heterogeneity¹²¹. One way to improve the performance of
186 these algorithms is to control the rotation of the protein as it is exposed to the XFEL pulse. This could
187 make SPI work with smaller sets of useful diffraction data, which would extend the application range
188 of this technique¹²². The protein rotation can be controlled by using static EFs that couple to the in-
189 trinsic dipole moment of the protein^{79,123}, or using lasers via a proteins' anisotropic polarizability¹²⁴.
190 However, these techniques have so far been described only theoretically. Efforts are currently be-
191 ing made to integrate EF-mediated orientation with native mass spectrometry to deliver well-defined
192 and homogeneous mass-selected and oriented protein complexes from heterogeneous mixtures for
193 SPI at the European XFEL^{128,129}. Marklund et al.⁷⁹ simulated gas-phase Trp-cage, a ribosome pro-
194 tein domain, ubiquitin and lysozyme under the influence of strong EFs and showed that there is an
195 “orientation window” of field strengths where proteins become oriented but with intact structures.
196 At field strength extending into the GV/m range the proteins started to unfold on a 10-ns timescale,
197 whereas for longer exposure times (50 ns) the window appeared to shift towards lower fields, Figure
198 2. Subsequent simulations using ramped fields that gradually increase from zero field strength, which
199 is more realistic than an instantaneous onset, indicated that ramping is better for preserving the struc-
200 ture, but also that protein orientation happens before unfolding – “orientation before destruction” –
201 meaning that a well-timed pulse could be used to image native-like structures also with destructive
202 field strengths¹²³. With the purpose to increase the dipole of the gas phase samples, to make the
203 orientation easier, simulations studies have explored the effect of adding a layer of water around the
204 protein¹³⁰. This seems to have some positive effects, at least for the protein simulated. The water
205 increases the total dipole slightly, but more importantly it tends to make the dipole more stable and
206 decreases the deviation between the protein structures, which is crucial for reaching high resolution

SPI. Another way to increase the dipole of proteins would be to add dipole enriching segments to the molecule itself, like chromophores¹³¹, but then again, it's important to understand how these affect the structure.

2.2 Effects on protein structure

Beyond translational and rotational rigid body-like motions, intense EF can significantly influence protein structure at various levels, including overall conformation, tertiary structure, and secondary structure, as well as size, shape, surface area, and unfolding behavior, see Tables 2, 3.

2.2.1 Effects on conformation and tertiary structure

Tertiary structure is the unique three-dimensional fold adopted by a single polypeptide chain, maintained by a network of hydrogen bonds, ionic contacts, hydrophobic packing and (in some proteins) covalent disulfide bridges that lock secondary structure elements into a precise spatial arrangement¹³². A conformation is any one of the inter-convertible spatial arrangements accessible to that folded chain on its rugged energy landscape; proteins continuously fluctuate among such conformers, and populations can shift in response to ligands, mutations or external stimuli⁴. Because active-site geometry, allosteric communication and molecular recognition all depend on both the native tertiary scaffold and its dynamic conformational ensemble, even subtle structural or energetic perturbations, such as those produced by EF, can switch enzymatic activity, redirect signalling pathways or promote misfolding and disease⁵.

MD simulations have shown extensively that intense EF can affect protein conformation^{68,78,82,123,126,133-15}. In larger proteins, even moderate external fields (10^5 – 10^7 V/m) influence the protein conformation. For example, fields two orders of magnitude weaker than typically required for protein damage caused the SARS-CoV-2 spike's receptor-binding β -sheet to unravel into an unstructured coil, abolishing its ability to bind ACE2¹²⁵. Similarly, a 30 MV/m static field applied to a GPCR (5-HT_{1A} receptor) drove an atypical inward shift of its transmembrane helix 6 and disrupted the normal activation by its agonist¹³⁵. Simulations have also shown that oscillating field can have distinct effects on the protein structure. A study on the effect on the structure of Alzheimer amyloid- β aggregates revealed that oscillating EFs (Os-EEF) in the low-frequency MHz–GHz range induce an “explosive” dissociation of peptide plaques, accompanied by the loss of their secondary structure, into monomers that do not reform (Figure 4). In contrast static fields (St-EEF) tend to align peptides into dipole-stabilized parallel bundles that recombine once the field is removed¹³³. This superiority of oscillating fields for irreversible disaggregation was observed consistently for both short fragments and full-length A β , and higher frequencies (THz) were paradoxically less effective. Notably, some proteins can tolerate very strong fields – enzymatic active sites can generate internal fields on the order of 100 MV/m – suggesting that external fields in the 0.1 – 1 MV/m range can be harnessed without catastrophic damage.

Experimental studies strongly support these predictions^{21,22,24,127,134,163,164}. Time-resolved crystallography using MV/m pulses has directly visualized Å-scale backbone and side-chain movements throughout a protein crystal, mirroring allosteric conformational changes²². Terahertz (THz) absorption and NMR experiments have shown that intense sub-THz irradiation perturbs protein–water dynamics nonthermally: in ubiquitin, a 0.1 THz field accelerates hydrogen-deuterium exchange at

247 buried amides while slowing exchange at surface loops, an effect opposite to uniform heating¹⁶³. Di-
248 electric relaxation measurements combined with NMR spectroscopy on lysozyme solutions similarly
249 found that sub-THz fields gradually lower the solvent permittivity by reorienting hydration water
250 into a more “hydrophobic” structuring around the protein, without bulk heating²⁴, and affect protein
251 conformation (Figure 3).

252 Real-time CD and autofluorescence studies were carried out for Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) and
253 lysozyme in solution for low-strength EFs. It was conjectured that for the low-intensity fields, unfold-
254 ing was caused by a frictional force generated by the electrophoretic motion of the proteins. Prolonged
255 exposure to an EF led the proteins to dissipate a large amount of frictional energy - indicating that
256 protein unfolding is a crucial first step for protein aggregation and also possibly for the formation of
257 amyloid fibrils¹⁶⁵. Complementarily, dynamic light scattering measurements resolved field-dependent
258 dynamical modes of BSA and interpreted them in terms of field-induced intermolecular interactions
259 in solution¹⁶⁶.

260 PEFs in the 0.1 MV/m range have also been widely applied to proteins in solution, revealing diverse
261 effects on protein conformation. Spectroscopic analyses (intrinsic fluorescence, circular dichroism
262 (CD), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR)) show that PEF treatments often partially unfold proteins,
263 reducing α -helix content and increasing disordered or β -sheet structures. This enhanced flexibility
264 can increase the exposure of functional sites: for instance, 1 MV/m PEF on pea protein cut its helix
265 fraction by 23% while doubling its binding capacity for the polyphenol EGCG (from 4 to 10 binding
266 sites, confirmed by docking), resulting in higher antioxidant performance¹²⁶, as illustrated in Figure
267 3b. In some cases, high-intensity PEF can even promote refolding; prawn tropomyosin treated at
268 2 MV/m underwent “extensive spiralization” into a tightly packed conformation, effectively masking
269 its IgE-binding epitopes and lowering allergenicity¹³⁴. By contrast, milder 0.5–1 MV/m pulses applied
270 to the same protein increased its flexibility and surface exposure, initially raising antibody reactivity
271 before eventual epitope masking at higher fields¹³⁴.

272 Functional assays corroborate that conformational changes translate into altered activity. Non-
273 thermal PEF inactivation of enzymes is one compelling example: a 0.25–1.25 MV/m pulse regime
274 targeting α -amylase caused 70% loss of activity by specifically disrupting a tryptophan-rich active-
275 site region, without the aggregation observed in thermal denaturation¹²⁷. Likewise, a brief 2 MV/m
276 PEF was found to affect conformation of α -amylase eliminating 80% of its activity when the en-
277 zyme was bound in an electrostatic complex with pectin¹⁶⁷. Despite this extensive conformational
278 damage, the PEF-treated enzyme–pectin complexes did not precipitate; instead, they assembled into
279 larger but soluble branched structures. Classical studies used intense EF on proteins or proteins-in-
280 membrane fragments in solutions. They used changes in protein sample refractive index anisotropy
281 as a real-time measure for protein conformational changes. For example, an electric pulse can induce
282 bacteriorhodopsin to transiently release and rebind protons at distinct sites, indicating that fields
283 perturb its proton-binding equilibrium¹⁶⁸. In dried purple membrane films, alternating high-voltage
284 fields cause complex absorbance changes that imply a multi-step cyclic conformational transition in
285 bacteriorhodopsin¹⁶⁹. Strong static fields drive a reversible spectral shift of purple bacteriorhodopsin
286 to its deprotonated “blue” form, with only a minor retinal rotation observed¹⁷⁰. In solution, mi-
287 crosecond field pulses reveal two distinct conformational phases in bacteriorhodopsin: an ultrafast
288 retinal reorientation followed by a slower protein charge rearrangement¹⁷¹. Early pulsed-field exper-

iments detected intramembrane structural changes with restricted chromophore motion in bacteriorhodopsin, and inferred an unusually high dipole polarizability as well as a five-state conformational cycle¹⁷². Even relatively weak fields (15 kV/m) can trigger a cooperative conformational change in bacteriorhodopsin (on a millisecond timescale)¹¹⁵.

These studies demonstrate that strong EFs—whether static, pulsed, or oscillating—offer a precise means to modulate protein conformation and often also a function. Potential uses range from physically inactivating pathogens and enzymes (e.g. “electro-denaturation” to weaken viral spikes or halt spoilage enzymes)¹²⁵, to enhancing food proteins’ digestibility and binding properties through conformational loosening¹²⁶, to novel therapeutic approaches like disrupting amyloid aggregates with oscillating fields¹³³. In parallel, the ability to trigger and probe conformational changes with fields (as in EF–X crystallography) is opening new avenues for mapping protein energy landscapes and allosteric pathways²².

2.2.2 Effects on secondary structure and unfolding

Proteins rely on well-defined secondary structure elements (α -helices, β -sheets, etc.) to maintain their three-dimensional fold and function, so even partial unfolding of these elements can lead to drastic loss of activity or aggregation. Because complex electrostatic interactions stabilize these structural motifs, external EF can readily perturb them: proteins’ abundant polar and charged groups make their conformations highly sensitive to applied EFs^{78,173}. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations have been instrumental in elucidating how intense EFs induce protein secondary structure changes and unfolding. *In silico* studies show that sufficiently strong fields can overcome native stabilizing forces and disrupt secondary structure, resulting in partial or complete unfolding. For example, simulations have demonstrated field-induced unfolding of globular proteins (such as myoglobin) and even induced transitions of secondary structure (e.g., converting β -sheet regions into α -helix or random coil conformations in peptides)⁷⁸. Notably, the unfolding process under a high field can follow relatively well-defined pathways, as observed in MD studies of gas-phase proteins subjected to extreme fields⁴⁷ (Figure 5), which could open up for studies folding and unfolding pathways experimentally. Even moderate-strength fields—within experimental reach—may trigger pronounced structural changes: one simulation found that a modest EF could destabilize the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein’s receptor-binding domain, converting a pair of β -strands into an unstructured loop and thereby abrogating its binding affinity¹²⁵. Similarly, recent MD work on Alzheimer’s amyloid- β ($A\beta$) peptides showed that an oscillating microwave-frequency field can rapidly diminish β -sheet content in $A\beta$ oligomers¹⁷⁴, and that applying either static or oscillating oriented fields can prevent aggregation and even irreversibly dissociate preformed amyloid fibrils in long simulations¹⁷⁵.

On the experimental front, a range of spectroscopic and biophysical techniques have been employed to probe EF-induced secondary structure changes and unfolding. Far-UV CD and FTIR spectroscopy provide direct readouts of secondary structure content (helix, sheet, turn), while intrinsic fluorescence (tryptophan emission) and extrinsic dye fluorescence assays (e.g., ANS or thioflavin T binding) report on tertiary structure exposure and amyloid formation; complementary methods such as light scattering, electron microscopy, and X-ray scattering have also been used to characterize aggregation state and structural dimensions under EFs^{173,176,177}. Using such methods, numerous studies have confirmed that EFs can induce significant secondary structure alterations and unfolding in prac-

330 tice. In an in situ CD study, Rodrigues et al. showed that applying a low-frequency moderate EF
331 during heating lowers the thermal denaturation midpoint of β -lactoglobulin and alters its unfold-
332 ing pathway, as evidenced by changes in CD spectra and increased hydrophobic surface exposure¹⁷⁸.
333 Peng et al. observed that high-frequency terahertz waves (~ 35 THz) act as a non-thermal denatur-
334 ing agent on A β amyloid, breaking apart β -sheet-rich fibrils and slowing fibrillization by $\sim 80\%$, as
335 indicated by reduced thioflavin T fluorescence and changes in FTIR spectra¹⁷⁷. PEFs, which deliver
336 transient high-voltage bursts, have emerged as an effective tool for modifying proteins in solution.
337 PEF treatments generally induce partial unfolding: for instance, mild PEF pretreatment (1.5 MV/m
338 pulses) of BSA caused the protein to become more disordered and partially unfolded, exposing hy-
339 drophobic regions that greatly enhanced its binding affinity and loading capacity for the hydrophobic
340 nutraceutical curcumin¹⁷⁹. At higher PEF intensities (≥ 2.5 MV/m) or longer exposures, however,
341 BSA's structure was overly disrupted, leading to diminished binding—illustrating that there is an op-
342 timal degree of unfolding for functional enhancement¹⁷⁹. Likewise, pulsed fields applied to soybean
343 protein isolates initially induced unfolding of quaternary and tertiary structures, depolymerizing large
344 protein aggregates via increased electrostatic repulsion, but above a threshold field strength this un-
345 folding became extensive enough to expose reactive groups that promoted irreversible aggregation
346 (through hydrophobic interactions and disulfide bond formation)¹⁸⁰. The ability to controllably per-
347 turb secondary structure with EFs carries broad implications and applications. In biotechnology and
348 food science, electric-field-induced unfolding offers a novel means to tune protein functionality—
349 improving solubility, emulsification, or ingredient binding by exposing buried segments, or guiding
350 protein assembly and gelation via controlled denaturation^{178–180}. In biomedical contexts, strong EFs
351 or electromagnetic fields provide a noninvasive strategy to modulate proteins: for example, to weaken
352 viral infection by structurally damaging key viral proteins¹²⁵, or to dissolve pathogenic protein aggre-
353 gates implicated in neurodegenerative diseases¹⁷⁵. Ongoing research combining external fields with
354 advanced time-resolved structural probes (e.g. ultrafast X-ray scattering or single-molecule imaging)
355 promises to further illuminate the mechanisms of EF-induced protein unfolding and to harness these
356 effects for innovative therapeutic and industrial applications⁴⁷.

357 2.3 Effects on energetic and thermodynamic properties

358 2.3.1 Free energy landscape

359 External EFs (\vec{E}) reshape protein free-energy landscapes by adding a field-dependent potential, $U_{\text{field}} =$
360 $-\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{E} = -\mu E \cos \theta$, that stabilises conformers with dipoles $\vec{\mu}$ aligned to the field. Atomistic simula-
361 tions consistently show that this energetic bias can split or funnel the landscape, modifying both
362 basin depths and barrier heights. In amyloidogenic apoC-II₆₀₋₇₀, a static field of 10–100 MV/m forced
363 $\sim 94\%$ dipole alignment, converting a single folded minimum into two distinct minima (compact
364 vs. extended) on the R_g -end-to-end free energy landscape and lowering the extended basin by ~ 5
365 kJ/mol¹⁵³. Model β -sheets display a comparable field sensitivity: above ~ 5 GV/m dielectric satura-
366 tion attenuates water shielding, shifts the balance of hydrophobic and electrostatic terms, and changes
367 the sheet-sheet binding free energy by tens of kJ/mol¹⁸⁴. Field-induced thermodynamic shifts are not
368 confined to backbone states. In thioredoxin, static EF as low as 20 MV/m were shown to lower the pK_a
369 of the buried Cys35 residue by 0.5–1.0 units, corresponding to a stabilization of the thiolate form by
370 3–6 kJ/mol in free energy. This field-induced shift reflects enhanced electrostatic polarization of the

active site, promoting deprotonation and thus favoring the catalytically competent state¹⁸², the PCA space was also significantly affected by 120 MV/m EF, see Fig. 6D. Nonequilibrium MD of chignolin revealed a striking contrast between static and 2.45 GHz alternating EF: whereas the static EF deepened the native basin, the oscillating EF flattened it and created a new metastable minimum, effectively redrawing the principal-component energy map (see Fig. 6) and accelerating state-hopping by an order of magnitude¹⁸¹. Replica-exchange MD on diphenylalanine showed an even stronger effect: a modest static EF collapsed a three-state landscape into a single dominant basin, reducing conformational entropy and producing a “funneled” surface across 310–373 K¹⁴⁴. Such entropy–enthalpy trade-offs underline how EF bias both minima and inter-state barriers. One strategy to quantify how an EF modifies protein stability is to compute field-dependent free-energy landscapes along a selected structural coordinate ξ —such as the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD), radius of gyration R_g , or a backbone principal component. Starting from a distribution $P_0(\xi)$ obtained under zero-field conditions, each protein conformation is assigned an interaction energy $U_{\text{field}}(\xi) = -\vec{\mu}(\xi) \cdot \vec{E}$, where $\vec{\mu}(\xi)$ is the dipole moment at coordinate value ξ and \vec{E} is the applied field vector. This energetic bias is used to reweight $P_0(\xi)$ using the Boltzmann factor $e^{-\beta U_{\text{field}}(\xi)}$ (with $\beta = 1/k_B T$), yielding a field-biased probability $P_E(\xi)$ and corresponding free energy $\Delta G(\xi, E) = -k_B T \ln P_E(\xi)$. This projection approach reveals how specific conformations are stabilized or destabilized by the EF. In a representative application¹⁸⁵, Baumketner employed umbrella sampling to map the folding free energy of poly-alanine under a static field of 0.1 GV/m, showing a ~ 10 kJ/mol reduction in the folding barrier. At the same time, this bias destabilized pre-assembled β -sheets, providing a thermodynamic explanation for field-induced disaggregation of amyloid structures. Free-energy perturbation calculations likewise show that GHz–THz fields can shift the minima associated with hydration-layer dipole orientations by several kJ mol⁻¹ without measurable bulk heating¹⁸⁶.

In the case of free-energy profiles of water-transport proteins, MD simulations of both static and alternating EF effects have been illuminating in the case of studying consequent dipolar orientation and role this has on regulating water transport through human aquaporin 4^{187,188}. The potentials of mean force were evaluated, as well as by using the more efficient metadynamics sampling method, to manipulate efficiently dipole-orientation in the transport channel, and studying water-flux effects, in a case of “field-enhanced” thermodynamic-state control for water-flux regulation. Direct sampling was required for assessing the shift in the potential of mean force by alternating EFs - ipso facto, owing to their time-dependent nature, whilst metadynamics approaches were found in both of these studies to be effective in enhancing statistical sampling and efficiency in the case of static (time-independent) fields. Indeed, the underlying statistical-mechanics framework for direct dipole-coupling to external EFs has been accomplished in non-equilibrium metadynamics, i.e., in using dipolar orientation as a direct collective variable per se, and this external-field control was applied to manipulate dipolar orientations of alanine¹⁸⁹.

Not all field strengths produce sizeable effects: QM/MM simulations of CO binding to solvated myoglobin found that a 1 GHz field below 10 MV/m altered the binding free energy by < 0.2 kJ/mol, implying a threshold above which thermal noise is overcome¹⁹⁰. Nevertheless, the 42.8 THz EF has been shown computationally to lower the permeation barrier of Ca²⁺ in Ca_v2.1 channels¹⁸³, and weak microwave fields subtly redistribute orientation-dependent collision free energies in carnosine solutions¹⁹¹. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that EF, when suitably tuned, can deepen, flatten

413 or bifurcate protein free-energy surfaces, thereby steering folding, binding, and aggregation pathways
414 in ways that would be inaccessible through temperature or chemical perturbation alone.

415 **2.3.2 Crystallization**

416 Protein crystallization is indispensable for both structural biology and bioseparations, yet obtaining
417 suitably large, well-ordered protein crystals remains notoriously challenging due to uncontrolled nu-
418 cleation and growth variability^{196,197}. A primary goal is often to grow a single large, defect-free crystal
419 for X-ray or neutron diffraction, which requires suppressing spurious nucleation events so that one nu-
420 cleus can consume the supersaturation¹⁹⁸. Intense external EFs have emerged as a promising tool to
421 tune protein-crystallization outcomes^{195,199}, often involving static EF (on the order of 0.1 MV/m)
422 or radio-frequency alternating current (AC) fields¹⁹². An applied field interacts with charged and
423 polar protein molecules, altering their spatial distribution and the chemical potential μ of protein in
424 solution and crystal phases^{195,200}. This can create local supersaturation zones and modify the nu-
425 cleation free-energy barrier ($\Delta\mu$), enabling either promotion or inhibition of nucleation depending
426 on field parameters^{195,201,202}. For example, an EF can orient protein dipoles and induce preferred
427 crystal orientation along the field direction¹⁹⁸, and it may modify intermolecular interactions enough
428 to suppress competing liquid–liquid phase separation in favor of direct crystallization¹⁹². Two general
429 modes of applying the field exist: an "internal" (or conducting) field with electrodes directly in the so-
430 lution (allowing a DC current through the sample), and an "external" (or non-conducting) field where
431 the electrodes are insulated or placed outside such that no electrolysis occurs^{201,203}. Indeed, new
432 device designs have been proposed and tested for external-electrode configurations, with some very
433 promising results to control and manipulate field-mediated crystallization precisely, with potential
434 applications for crystallization in, inter alia, the lipidic cubic phase²⁰⁴.

435 In typical DC-field crystallization, the protein (often carrying net charge in solution) electro-
436 migrates toward an electrode, quickly establishing a high-concentration (supersaturated) region near
437 that electrode^{200,205}. Consequently, nucleation is preferentially localized at the electrode and is
438 largely suppressed in the bulk or at the anode, yielding a reduced number of crystals, usually only
439 one or few, growing at the cathodic interface^{200,206}. This method drastically reduces the overall
440 nucleation rate while accelerating the first nucleation event (shortening induction time) and pro-
441 duces larger crystals than for zero-field controls^{200,206}. Indeed, crystals grown under a static EF (DC)
442 are often significantly bigger and exhibit improved diffraction quality (e.g., lower "mosaicity" and
443 higher resolution) due to the minimization of simultaneous nucleation events^{200,207}. In contrast, an
444 alternating-current EF (especially at high frequency) can be applied without net electro-migration,
445 influencing crystallization through pure electrostatic effects on the free-energy landscape^{195,196}. AC
446 fields have been shown to either enhance or inhibit protein nucleation by tuning the field frequency
447 to adjust the electrostatic contribution to the phase free energies^{195,202}. Notably, under a 1 MHz AC
448 field, lysozyme crystals grew more slowly (with reduced growth kinetics), despite an increased super-
449 saturation driving force, as the field effectively raised the step-edge free energy and produced flatter,
450 more orderly crystal faces; this led to substantially improved crystal perfection (fewer defects and
451 lower mosaic spread) in the tetragonal lysozyme form^{196,208}. Many studies report that EFs can expe-
452 ditede the nucleation of proteins that are otherwise difficult to crystallize: for instance, the application
453 of an extremely low-voltage (~ 1 V, 20 Hz) internal field was sufficient to induce thaumatin crystal-

lization in a regime where no crystals normally appeared²⁰⁹. Likewise, microfluidic experiments with patterned ITO electrodes demonstrated that certain AC field configurations could both reduce nucleation induction time and localize crystal formation to specific sites, even enabling insulin crystals to form in cases where control samples showed none^{197,210}.

The presence of an EFs offers remarkable control over crystallization kinetics: it can reduce induction times, control the number and location of nuclei, increase crystal size, and enhance crystal quality (yielding larger and more orderingly packed crystals) under a broad range of conditions^{193,199,211}. This approach has been successfully leveraged to improve protein crystal homogeneity and diffraction properties for structural analysis^{207,211}, to manipulate crystal polymorphs by stabilizing a desired solid phase through field-induced $\Delta\mu$ shifts²⁰², and even to achieve oriented crystallization for better crystal mounting or data collection^{198,199}. Continued advances in electric-field-assisted crystallization techniques – including scaling up to continuous crystallizers and combining fields with other stimuli – highlight the significant implications of this approach for both fundamental protein crystallography and practical protein manufacturing^{199,212}.

2.4 Effects on electrostatic, mechanical and dynamic properties

2.4.1 Effective electric charge and dipole, local electrostatic environment

In a protein, charged residues are arranged in a defined three-dimensional pattern. Their algebraic sum determines the protein's overall net charge, while their spatial distribution creates the molecule's permanent dipole moment. The effects of EFs on the protein dipole moment have been extensively studied using MD simulations^{46,213–215}. How the EFs affect protein behavior was shown by Marracino et al., who investigated the polarization of the myoglobin protein in response to a pulsed/static EF of 0.1 GV/m to 1 GV/m strength¹⁵⁹. It was observed that nsPEF of 1 GV/m strength induced a fast transition (within few hundreds picoseconds) of the protein dipole moment and the protein remained highly polarized even after switching off the pulse during the simulation. The effects observed in this case of nsPEF were very similar to those obtained after exposure to static EF. Another interesting effect was the increase of the dipole moment after exposure with EF of lower strength (100 MV/m). At this strength, the EF did not have any major effect on the secondary structure or overall geometry of the protein despite causing significant polarization. This slow kinetics/magnitude of polarization (upon exposure with lower strength EF) indicated subtle changes in the structure, which might be a very helpful finding for bio-nanotechnology applications, in which protein structure could be manipulated without causing any denaturation effects.

Tubulin proteins, carrying an unusually high charge and dipole moment⁷⁸, are the building unit of microtubules, which makes them a target for investigation of EF effects. Apart from the effects of EF on the mechanical properties of tubulin protein mentioned above,^{218,219} Marracino et al. studied the temporal evolution of the dipole moment of a tubulin dimer as well as of individual residues that form the binding sites for various drug molecules and cofactors such as GTP/GDP⁷⁸. Applying EF of strength 10 MV/m to 300 MV/m resulted in the polarization of the dimer, which led to a change in the shape and orientation of tubulin dimer. Data showed that the dipole component along the median axis (containing a highly charged C-terminal tail) is affected most, causing the C-terminal tail to extend beyond the dimer surface. The EF also affected the dipole moment of residues in the binding sites and this polarization effect varied with the strength of applied EF. The analysis of the dipole moment

495 in this study could be helpful in other cases such as protein-drug interactions, in which the binding
496 of a drug can be controlled by applying an EF, or in ion channels, in which the conductance can be
497 manipulated by the effect of an external EF on the orientation of charged residues in loops.
498 Marracino et al.²²⁰ used MD simulations to test whether classical Onsager–Kirkwood theory—valid
499 under “weak field” linear-response conditions—still holds for nanosecond, high-intensity continuous-
500 wave (CW) EFs. Unlike the static or ideal rectangular fields common in MD studies, real nsPEF
501 waveforms possess finite rise/fall times that broaden their spectra into the 100 MHz–100 GHz range.
502 The authors showed that CW amplitudes above ~ 150 MV/m drive pronounced nonlinear behaviour
503 throughout this band: higher-order polarization harmonics emerge, especially at the lower frequen-
504 cies, but fade beyond the dipolar relaxation limit. The simulated polarization follows a Langevin-type
505 curve; by adapting the Langevin function and introducing a frequency-dependent correlation $P(\omega)$,
506 they built a predictive dipolar-interaction model ($R^2 \approx 1$) that naturally reproduces the Debye-like
507 water relaxation time. Their results highlight the need to keep field strengths below ~ 200 MV/m in
508 protein MD studies to remain within the weak-field regime and avoid nonlinear or saturation arte-
509 facts²²¹.

510 Protein electrostatics plays a fundamental role in shaping the structure, maintaining the stability,
511 and governing the function of proteins through the spatial arrangement and interaction of internal
512 charge distributions. As outlined in the Introduction, protein electrostatics is essential for processes
513 such as molecular recognition and catalytic activity^{40,41}. Intense EFs interact with proteins and lead
514 to altered charge distributions, often mediated by water polarization. MD simulations reveal that
515 EFs in the range of 0.1–1 GV/m can modify electrostatic environments without structural damage at
516 lower intensities, while higher intensities may induce unfolding. For example, in superoxide dismu-
517 tase (SOD1)²¹⁶, fields of 100 MV/m affect the electrostatic environment of the active site, enhancing
518 substrate interaction. Similarly, in tubulin, fields above 20 MV/m induce significant change of dipole
519 components of several functionally important residues⁷⁸. Stark spectroscopy, particularly the vibra-
520 tional Stark effect²²², is a key technique for studying protein electrostatics by measuring how local
521 EFs influence vibrational probe frequencies, such as nitrile stretches. This spectroscopy offers insights
522 into electrostatic forces within proteins, revealing their magnitude and direction, and was demon-
523 strated to sense changes in internal protein electrostatics when applied 100 MV/m EF (myoglobin in
524 glycerol/water glass at 74 K)^{223,224}.

525 2.4.2 Nanomechanics of proteins

526 Mechanical properties, including stiffness, elasticity, and force resistance, are fundamental determi-
527 nants of protein function, because the mechanical energy stored and released by folded domains
528 powers conformational transitions that enable catalysis, ligand gating, mechanotransduction, and
529 allosteric regulation^{229,230}. Therefore, understanding how EFs influence protein function requires ex-
530 amining their impact on protein mechanics – a topic that has been explored through MD simulations
531 under applied fields.

532 Microtubules (MT) form the cellular skeleton and guide mitosis, motility, and organelle transport¹³² [Section 18
533 Since the subunits of MT, $\alpha\beta$ -tubulin dimers are strongly charged, they can couple to external EF.
534 Saedi et al.²¹⁸ pulled the tubulin dimer via a virtual spring while subject to EF in MD simulation:
535 a static 30 MV/m field softened the dimer, whereas a 1 GHz field of the same amplitude stiffened

it; at 10 GHz the response was negligible because the field direction flipped too rapidly for effective coupling. Using the same protocol, Setayandeh & Lohrasebi²¹⁹ showed that 30 MV/m fields at 5 GHz increased rigidity of dimer pairs along the MT axis, whereas 1 and 6 GHz fields enhanced flexibility, mimicking taxol-stabilising effect. These studies demonstrate that EFs have the potential to modulate protein nanomechanics to achieve diverse functional outcomes, and can also be harnessed as a force handle in electromechanical force spectroscopy.

2.5 Effects on protein interactions

Protein interactions, encompassing both protein–protein interactions (PPIs) and protein–ligand (throughout our text, "ligand" refers to non-protein molecule) interactions (PLIs), are fundamental to biological function and the assembly of quaternary structures. Such interactions drive the self-assembly of protein complexes, protein oligomers and polymers, and regulate processes ranging from enzymatic catalysis to signal transduction. The intermolecular forces stabilizing these complexes (hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic contacts, electrostatic interactions, etc.) can be sensitive to external perturbations like EF, allowing to influence their conformation and interaction propensity. From a thermodynamic standpoint, protein-protein interfaces are especially appealing targets for EF perturbation, because dissociating them entails overcoming a lower energy barrier than that required to trigger structural changes in individual proteins, such as unfolding²³¹.

2.5.1 Protein-protein interactions: quaternary structure, multimeric complexes, fibrils and polymers

State-of-the-art molecular-dynamics simulations spanning sub-nanosecond to microsecond scales reveal how EF from 0.01 to 1 GV/m tilt the free-energy landscape of PPIs. Radio-frequency EF of 30 MV/m weakened the kinesin–tubulin interface by $\sim 20\%$ ²³² which could lead to disrupted stepping kinetics; a paclitaxel-stabilised lattice showed even lower kinesin affinity under identical conditions²³³. Beyond cytoskeletal proteins, static EF of 0.1–1 GV/m aligned peptide dipoles, favouring α -helical states and dissolving pre-assembled β -sheets¹⁸⁵. For A β oligomers, dimers and trimers unraveled whereas pentamers kept an intact hydrophobic core, implying a size-dependent stability threshold^{214,234}. ApoC-II₆₀₋₇₀ displayed a triphasic response: rather weak EF (<7 MV/m) promoted β -hairpins that seed fibrils, intermediate fields (40–70 MV/m) disrupted this motif, and stronger fields elongated the peptide along the field vector, preventing aggregation¹⁵³. Prusa et al.⁴⁶ studied EF effects on a 13-protofilament ring of tubulin heterodimers (periodically repeated to represent a microtubule wall) fully solvated with ions, and was exposed to static EF of 50 or 100 MV/m. EF orientation, magnitude and temperature, but not the ionic strength, influenced MT integrity: both field strengths repeatedly open the lattice at the protofilament lateral interface, always on the cathodic side, see Fig. 10. The study suggested that such openings may modulate MT stability and the rates of polymerisation and depolymerisation. Across these studies, electro-torque on permanent dipoles, dielectric polarisation, and field-driven water ordering emerged as common microscopic drivers.

Electrowetting-on-dielectric (EWOD) stacks platforms confine the applied voltage to the solid PDMS/Teflon dielectric and the nanometre-thin electrical double layer, leaving the interior of the micro- to nanolitre droplet virtually field-free. The resulting Maxwell stress at the three-phase line drives controllable droplet deformations that can be tracked *in situ*. Sen et al. used this oscilla-

576 tory actuation to fragment pre-formed HSA fibrils in a sharply frequency-dependent manner, cutting
577 ThT fluorescence by 60% at the 20 Hz optimum²³⁵. An analogous EWOD geometry biased with a
578 static 8 MV//m EF²²⁷ produced a comparable loss of fibril β -sheet content, confirmed by CD, AFM
579 and TEM (Fig. 9E). Because the EF scarcely penetrates the liquid in EWOD platforms, both studies
580 most likely induce bulk hydrodynamic shear (see Section 3 on Indirect EF effects) and interfacial
581 electro-compression rather than a direct bulk-field effect on the proteins.

582 Intense picosecond THz pulses provide a complementary route. Using 0.15–3 THz bursts with
583 peak fields 40 MV/m, Hough et al. showed that polymerised microtubules disassembled within min-
584 utes (Fig. 11C); the rate scaled with both field amplitude and spectral content, and band-pass filtering
585 revealed maximum efficacy near 0.5 THz²⁵. At the level of tubulin dimers, Chafai et al. exposed
586 purified protein to a train of 2 MV/m, 10 ns EF pulses and found a dose-dependent shift from normal
587 nucleation–elongation kinetics to suppressed assembly, tracked by turbidimetry, intrinsic fluorescence
588 and zeta-potential changes; below 200 pulses the effect was largely reversible, whereas ≥ 400 pulses
589 produced persistent inhibition²¹, with 800 pulses leading to changed self-assembled tubulin structure
590 as probed by AFM, see Fig. 11B. Analogous disassembly-promoting behaviour of the intense EF is
591 observed with pathogenic protein aggregates. Jurgelevičiūtė et al. treated isolated Sup35NM prion
592 fibrils with PEF (10 pulses, their 50 or 1000 μ s). The AFM imaging revealed progressive shorten-
593 ing and, at 2 MV/m, complete breakup into oligomers, see Fig. 11A. Actin responded oppositely to
594 continuous-wave 0.46 THz irradiation (power density $\approx 0.6 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$), which accelerated the elon-
595 gation phase of *in-vitro* actin polymerisation, generating 3.5-fold more filaments without detectable
596 denaturation, as verified by SiR-actin microscopy and pyrene fluorescence²³⁶.

597 In the case of PPI in amorphous-protein aggregation, aggregates of amorphous proteins were sub-
598 jected to an oscillating EF. When their field response was observed using time-resolved polarized op-
599 tical microscopy, they revealed the disintegration of large aggregate clusters as well as field-induced
600 deformation, reorientation, and enhanced polarization. Further, amorphous aggregate suspensions'
601 collective microscopic dynamics were investigated using small-angle dynamic light scattering. The in-
602 tensity auto-correlation function exhibited field-enhanced local oscillations that were associated with
603 two distinct elastic moduli – drawing attention to the potential of EFs to regulate protein-aggregation
604 processes²³⁷.

605 PEFs (0.1–3 MV/m, μ s bursts) are widely used in food processing to affect PPI: ovalbumin at
606 neutral pH aggregated modestly, whereas at pH 4 or 9 it remained monomeric²²⁸. Soybean proteins
607 showed a biphasic trend—0.5–1.5 MV/m unfolded tetramers and released subunits, but ≥ 2 MV/m
608 exposed hydrophobes and thiols that re-cross-linked the proteins¹⁸⁰, see also Fig. 9B. Time-resolved
609 fluorescence and Ellman assays pinpointed radical generation as a secondary pathway, indicating also
610 indirect electrochemical effects of EF taking place (see Section 3.2). For the allergen tropomyosin,
611 0.5–1 MV/m bursts opened coiled-coil dimers and raised IgE binding by ~ 30 %, whereas prolonged
612 or stronger treatment compacted the structure and lowered immunoreactivity¹³⁴.

613 Together, these studies demonstrate that intense static, pulsed or THz-frequency EFs can decisively
614 remodel protein–protein contacts (from weakening kinesin–tubulin binding and accelerating actin
615 growth to fragmenting amyloid) highlighting a versatile, rapidly switchable handle for manipulating
616 quaternary, multimeric and polymeric protein structure *in vitro* and *in vivo*: The selective dismant-
617 tling of amyloid fibrils or weakening of motor–track contacts suggests non-invasive anti-aggregation

therapies and neuromodulation strategies^{133,237}. Conversely, reinforcing or creating PPIs with tuned EF could stabilise fragile enzyme assemblies in biosensors or power nanobiomachines. In agri-food technology, PEF was demonstrated to deliver chemical-free control of gel texture, solubility and allergenicity^{134,180,228}

2.5.2 Effects on protein - ligand binding

Precise binding of proteins to their ligands, substrates, and co-factors underlies essential biological functions – from enzyme catalysis and metabolic regulation to signal transduction. Emerging evidence indicates that intense external EFs can modulate these interactions by reshaping protein conformations and intermolecular forces. MD simulations have revealed atomic-level effects: for example, applying a static field of 30 MV/m to a GPCR (5-HT_{1A} receptor)–serotonin complex caused an inward shift of an α -helix (TM6) that perturbed serotonin binding and receptor activation¹³⁵. By contrast, a mixed quantum-classical simulation of myoglobin covalently binding CO under a 1 GHz microwave EF found no significant perturbation at field strengths far below intrinsic molecular forces, implying a threshold EF strength is required to alter ligand-binding kinetics¹⁹⁰. Experimentally, a variety of spectroscopic techniques (fluorescence quenching assays, CD, UV–Vis absorption, etc.) have been used to monitor field-induced changes in protein structure and binding. These studies show that EFs can both stabilize and disrupt binding interactions depending on conditions. For instance, *in situ* CD and fluorescence of β -lactoglobulin under moderate AC fields revealed field-dependent unfolding with increased surface hydrophobicity (ANS dye binding) yet a preserved affinity for its native ligand (retinol), indicating a distinct partially-unfolded state retaining co-factor binding¹⁷⁸. Terahertz irradiation of serum albumin (3–4 THz) similarly induced subtle secondary-structure alterations and dose-dependent changes in hormone (progesterone) binding capacity²³⁹. In the context of PEF - a *non-thermal* high-intensity treatment - numerous studies demonstrate enhanced binding or reaction outcomes due to field-induced protein polarization and partial unfolding. PEF pretreatment of BSA at 1.5 MV/m, for example, increased the curcumin–BSA binding constant by nearly 7-fold by exposing buried hydrophobic pockets, whereas exceeding 2.5 MV/m led to over-denaturation and weakened affinity¹⁷⁹. Likewise, PEF-assisted Maillard reactions of BSA with glucose or starch yielded higher glycation degrees and superior emulsifying properties, attributed to field-driven unfolding that increased reactive site exposure (with optimal E-field ranges of 0.3–1.5 MV/m before deleterious effects set in)^{240,241}. On the other hand, intense PEF can impair function: applying 2 MV/m to enzyme–polysaccharide complexes caused aggregate β -sheet formation and an ~80% loss of α -amylase activity, underscoring the disruptive extreme of field exposure¹⁶⁷.

These findings illustrate that strong EF are potent modulators of protein-ligand/substrate binding, capable of enhancing interactions (by transiently altering conformation to improve ligand accessibility and binding affinity) or inhibiting them (via induced unfolding or misfolding). This knowledge opens up opportunities for innovative applications – from non-thermal control of enzymatic reactions and protein processing (e.g. tailored glycation and improved drug/nutrient binding) to the remote tuning of receptor activation and protein function in biomedical and biotechnological settings.

2.6 Effects on additional protein functions

2.6.1 Enzymatic function

Large class of proteins function as enzymes to catalyze essential biochemical reactions in living systems and industry, exhibiting remarkable specificity and efficiency²⁴⁶. Enzymatic activity depends on the protein's structure and chemical environment, so external perturbations like intense EF can alter function by inducing conformational changes or modifying active-site properties. For example, simulations show static fields can lower the pK_a of a catalytic cysteine (thioredoxin Cys35) by altering electrostatics¹⁸², and experimental nanosecond 1 MV/m pulses can eject a Zn^{2+} cofactor from a zinc-dependent enzyme, inactivating it (Fig. 13C) without global unfolding²⁴³. Experimentally, PEFs (PEFs) often inactivate enzymes non-thermally by inducing partial unfolding. Significant activity loss with corresponding secondary and tertiary structure changes has been observed in many enzymes: e.g., horseradish peroxidase and papain show reduced activity (on the order of 20–50%) and α -helix content after PEF treatment, despite minimal heating^{162,242,247}, see Fig. 13A,B. In milk, PEF achieved $\sim 90\%$ inactivation of plasmin protease under mild conditions²⁴⁸. The sensitivity to PEF is enzyme-specific: some enzymes (lipase, glucose oxidase) lose $>70\%$ activity while others (alkaline phosphatase) are much more resistant or even activated (lysozyme, pepsin) under high-field pulses²⁴⁹. Similarly, exposure to microwave-frequency fields (~ 10 GHz) can irreversibly inactivate thermophilic enzymes via structural rearrangements, independent of bulk heating²⁵⁰. Furthermore, PEF can affect enzyme function within complex food matrices: in α -amylase–pectin mixtures, PEF caused $\sim 80\%$ activity loss and promoted aggregation of enzyme–polysaccharide complexes¹⁶⁷. Mechanistic studies point to specific molecular targets: PEF was shown to act on tryptophan residues in α -amylase's active site, disrupting its conformation and reducing activity by $\sim 70\%$ without the aggregation seen in heat denaturation¹²⁷. Even extremely high-frequency fields (~ 100 GHz) can subtly affect enzymes: for instance, 100 GHz irradiation slightly reduced alkaline phosphatase activity and destabilized antigen–antibody binding when the proteins were free in solution (but not when immobilized), suggesting effects via altered molecular rotations or vibrations¹⁶⁴. Conversely, under certain conditions EFs can enhance enzymatic activity, see Fig. 13E. A moderate (0.1 kV/m) oscillating field at low frequency (1–60 Hz) increased α -amylase activity by up to $\sim 41\%$, an effect disappearing at higher frequencies²⁴⁶. Likewise, PEF at ~ 1.5 MV/m boosted α -amylase activity by $\sim 22\%$, broadening its temperature optimum and improving kinetic parameters (lower K_m , higher V_{max}), concomitant with a slight increase in α -helix structure²⁴⁵. A mild PEF (~ 1 MV/m) also enhanced alcalase protease activity ($\sim 11\%$), apparently via partial unfolding that improved substrate accessibility, as supported by molecular docking analysis²⁴⁴. These findings carry important implications. PEF-based enzyme inactivation has clear applications in food preservation: it can deactivate spoilage enzymes or unwanted enzymatic activity while preserving food quality, as demonstrated by non-thermal PEF treatments that maintain flavor/nutrients²⁴² and effectively inactivate enzymes like plasmin in milk²⁴⁸. PEF can also halt enzyme-driven processes at desired endpoints; for example, $\sim 70\%$ PEF inactivation of a commercial protease mix (Protamex) was sufficient to stop protein hydrolysis in a food matrix without heating²⁵¹. On the other hand, gentle field treatments can be harnessed to improve beneficial enzymatic processes: pretreating whey protein with high-voltage pulses greatly increased its subsequent digestibility by trypsin/chymotrypsin, boosting the yield of bioactive peptides²⁵². Thus, depending on EF strength and exposure, EFs can either diminish enzyme function via structural disruption (or cofac-

tor removal) or enhance it by modulating conformation, offering a novel means to control enzymatic activity in various applications.

2.6.2 Membrane proteins function

Trans-membrane proteins Another important application of EF in trans-membrane proteins lies in electroporation – which, in and of itself, is becoming more important in the expanding fields of nanomedicine and in electro-chemotherapy. This rupture of a phospholipid-bilayer membrane – pivotal to structural stability of biomaterials - can be brought about by a strong externally-applied EF. This connects the cytosol and cytoplasm, with greater degrees of permeability of water, and, possibly, ions in most cell lines²⁵³ not typically permitted through; of course, this depends on the limiting solubility of the solute in the aqueous solvent²⁵⁴, and is affected by the electrostatic environment²⁵⁵ inside such cells for conductivity²⁵⁶ and diffusivity²⁵⁷. Indeed, the manipulation of electroporation may allow for drug-free therapies in medicine and ion transport in desalination, and a particularly “case study” of such electroporation phenomena in trans-membrane proteins lies in aquaporins. In mammalian life, eleven different aquaporins (AQPs) have been reported²⁵⁸, and they all play different roles in different locations of the body. In humans, urea production and water retention in kidneys²⁵⁹ are among the most important AQP-controlled process; also if the protein is genetically defective, it can lead to diabetes²⁶⁰ and polyurea. In recent times, Marracino et al. applied MD with EF to render an electropore stable in h-AQP4 for extended periods of tens of nanoseconds, seeing at first hand novel phenomena of electropore formation within trans-membrane proteins, as opposed to the phospholipid bilayer²⁶¹. There, the tetramer configuration can facilitate, under certain field-mediated situations, the formation of this ‘fifth-pore’ pore along the tetramer’s axis; this arises due to dipole coupling of some protein residues with the applied field²⁶¹ (vide infra). The approach was adapted to give rise to a stable pore^{261,262}, inside a maintaining EF and a sustaining EF. It was remarked, in passing, in ref.²⁶¹, that this pore metastability, brings about occasional ion-permeation events via pores. As Marracino et al. found, it is the ready dipole alignment of ASP69 which brings about the action of membrane poration per se²⁶¹. We note that Bernardi et al. performed more detailed MD studies on field-driven ionic permeability through these h-AQP4 electro-pores, including a mechanistic and statistical study of permeation events²⁶³, building on analysis techniques of diffusivity and permeability calculations of ref.²⁶⁴. Recently, ionic permeation has been found through a pore formed in a human-AQP4 trans-membrane protein subject to a static EF^{263,265}. Recently, CaCl salt has been studied for AQP ionic conductivity through electropores²⁶⁵, although this study was focussed more specifically on dwell-time and mean-first-passage-time distributions.

Similarly in²⁶⁶ it is shown that PEFs can induce pores in the voltage-sensor domains of different voltage gated transmembrane channels. Such fields can create conductive pores which evolve into complex pores stabilized by lipid molecules followed by unfolding of the voltage sensor domain from the channel. The mechanism is related to the degree of hydration of the sensor: the more hydrated the sensor is, the more electrostatically favorable for the entry of ions will be, and the more easily it porates.

Experimental EF effects were demonstrated on membrane proteins as part of isolated membranes or in cells. One class of works exploited electro-optical approaches mentioned above. A common target protein was bacteriorhodopsin in purple membrane, in which pulsed EF induced pH

739 change^{168,269,270}, structural effects^{112,115,171,172} and DC- or AC-field caused conformational changes^{110,169,170}.
740 Another class of works focused on oscillating EF effects on ATPases: pulsed EF drove the ATP syn-
741 thesis²⁷¹ and AC fields drove cation transport across the membrane in a resonant-like manner²⁷²
742 (Rb^+ ²⁷³, Na^+ ²⁷⁴). Follow-up works generalized the concept and proposed that enzymes can harness
743 energy from various EF waveforms^{275–279}, including stochastic ones^{280–282}, using electroconforma-
744 tional coupling model.

745 2.6.3 Photonic/luminescence functional properties

746 Proteins often exhibit intrinsic and extrinsic fluorescence or luminescence, which are crucial for prob-
747 ing their structure and function *in vitro* and *in vivo*²⁸³. These photonic properties (emission inten-
748 sity, spectrum, polarization, etc.) are sensitive to the protein's environment, and external EFs can
749 markedly influence them. Strong static EFs, for example, can perturb the energy levels of a protein
750 chromophore (Stark effect), leading to spectral shifts or fluorescence quenching if the excited-state
751 dipole differs from the ground state²⁸³. Insights from theory and MD simulations suggest that ex-
752 tremely high field strengths ($\sim 10^7$ V/m) are often required to observe non-thermal effects on protein
753 electronic states²⁸⁴. Notably, proteins' own internal electrostatic fields of similar magnitude can also
754 modulate chromophore fluorescence by restricting molecular motions²⁸⁵. Experimentally, EF effects
755 on protein fluorescence have been investigated using various approaches. Electrofluorescence spec-
756 troscopy under DC fields reveals field-induced fluorescence quenching in GFP mutants (attributed
757 to an EF-enhanced non-radiative decay rate)²⁸³. In the microwave regime, intense alternating fields
758 (GHz frequencies) induce changes in fluorescence emission anisotropy, indicating orientational effects
759 beyond ordinary thermal heating²⁸⁴. Conversely, static fields up to 10^7 V/m applied to immobilized
760 proteins (e.g., the metalloprotein azurin) caused no detectable change in intrinsic tryptophan fluores-
761 cence, implying no significant EF-induced unfolding²⁸⁶. Such results demonstrate that many proteins
762 can withstand very strong EFs without loss of function, a promising sign for bioelectronic applica-
763 tions that integrate proteins into high-field environments²⁸⁶. At the same time, the ability to tune
764 protein luminescence with external fields provides a novel avenue for controlling optical signals and
765 developing advanced spectroscopic probes of protein dynamics^{283,284,286–288}.

766 3 Indirect effects of EF exposure

767 The EF applied to protein solutions can impart a variety of *indirect* stresses on the proteins via physical
768 and chemical changes in the surrounding medium. These indirect effects are distinguished from the
769 *direct* interactions of the EF with the protein's molecular structure described in the sections above, and
770 instead involve secondary phenomena like heating, fluid motion, shockwave generation, electrolysis-
771 driven pH shifts, reactive chemical species formation, and gas bubble formation. Such effects come
772 into play for high-field exposures across the spectrum of DC, AC, pulsed, radio-frequency (RF), and
773 microwave fields, especially at field strengths of the order of 0.1 MV/m and above. In this section,
774 we review the major indirect mechanisms by which intense EFs can influence protein structure and
775 stability. We exclude cases that involve plasma formation or dielectric breakdown (sparking), focusing
776 instead on sub-breakdown conditions where the field-induced effects are non-ionizing. The indirect
777 pathways are categorized into electrophysical effects – arising from the physical consequences of the
778 EF (such as thermal and mechanical perturbations) – and electrochemical effects – arising from field-
779 induced chemical reactions or species in the solution. All types of proteins (enzymes, structural pro-

teins, antibodies, etc.) can be susceptible to these indirect stressors, although their specific responses may vary depending on factors like stability, size, and environment.

3.1 Indirect electrophysical effects of EF

3.1.1 Heat generation

One of the main indirect effects of intense EF in conductive solutions is Joule (ohmic, resistive) heating. When an EF E is applied across a medium with conductivity σ , heat is generated at a rate $P = \sigma E^2$. Similarly, microwave and RF fields (GHz range) deposit energy in lossy dielectrics (i.e. those with imaginary part of relative permittivity $\epsilon'' > 0$, such as water, via dipolar rotation, leading to dielectric heating at a rate $P = \omega \epsilon_0 \epsilon'' E^2$, where ω is angular frequency of EF, and ϵ_0 is permittivity of vacuum. At EF strengths of 0.1 MV/m or higher, this can rapidly raise solution temperatures by tens of degrees Celsius unless controlled. Proteins are sensitive to temperature: many enzymes and antibodies unfold between 40–80°C²⁹⁴. For instance, Zhao et al. showed that strong EF applied in capillaries caused measurable temperature rises and corresponding unfolding of myoglobin, cytochrome c, and carbonic anhydrase II, with more stable proteins requiring more heat to denature²⁹⁵. Localized heating near electrodes or in hotspots can further intensify damage²⁹⁶, leading to precipitation or aggregation. Even short pulses can generate non-uniform heating in boundary layers. All these effects have to be mitigated (cooling, and short pulse protocols) or accounted for using electromagnetic and thermal simulations²⁹⁷ as well as experimental temperature monitoring²⁹⁸ isolating true EF effects from heat artifacts.

3.1.2 Heat and EF induced flows

Intense EFs can induce fluid motion through several mechanisms that contribute to indirect effects on proteins²⁹⁹. Key flow types include: (1) *electrothermal convection* from temperature gradients due to Joule³⁰⁰ or dielectric^{301,302} heating or thermophoresis³⁰³; (2) *electrokinetic flows*, such as electroosmosis/symmetry-broken electrophoresis and dielectrophoresis^{304–308}.

In practice, electroosmotic contributions are strongest when charged interfaces (electrodes, channel walls, bubbles) are present and the electrical double layer can charge within the field period. The characteristic charging time τ_c sets a frequency crossover: for $\omega \tau_c \gtrsim 1$ (often $\gtrsim 10$ – 100 kHz in microscale geometries) AC electroosmosis diminishes markedly, whereas at 0.1– 10 kHz it can generate steady vortical flows even at modest fields of order kV/m^{304–306}. Consequently, flow-induced hydrodynamic interactions can be important in concentrated protein suspensions and near-wall geometries where long-ranged flows enhance collision rates and promote field-assisted aggregation or adsorption. In contrast, in dilute bulk solution away from boundaries (typical for many spectroscopic assays), direct electrophoretic/dielectrophoretic and dipolar interactions between proteins are usually the dominant field couplings, while electroosmotic flow mainly enters indirectly by redistributing heat and reactive species^{299,308}.

These flows have dual consequences. On the one hand, they improve heat and species transport and mixing, preventing localized extremes of temperature or electrochemically produced species that would otherwise damage proteins. On the other hand, flow also introduces hydrodynamic shear and increases contact between proteins and interfaces, such as gas bubbles or electrodes, where adsorption and unfolding can occur³⁰⁹. In summary, EF-induced flows can either protect or damage proteins

820 depending on their magnitude and context. Controlling flow regimes is therefore essential in high-
821 field experimental design.

822 3.1.3 Shockwaves

823 Rapid energy deposition by a nanosecond PEF makes the liquid expand faster than it can relax
824 acoustically, launching a shockwave—an abrupt, high-frequency pressure transient. A single 600 ns,
825 1.3 MV/m pulse between micro-electrodes produced a 2.5 MHz, >13 kPa wave in saline, confirming
826 that ns-PEF creates measurable shocks³¹⁰. Peak loads of 10–100 kPa are too small and transient to
827 unfold globular proteins, which typically require sustained pressures ≥ 200 MPa³¹¹. More damaging
828 is the cavitation seeded during the negative-pressure tail of the wave: nanosecond optical diagnostics
829 have visualised voids at -20 to -30 MPa in pulsed needle-electrode fields³¹². Imploding bubbles reach
830 4 000–5 000 K and hundreds of bar, emitting radical species, micro-jets and secondary shocks that can
831 damage biomolecules^{313,314} similarly to the electrochemistry processes outlined lower. Macroscopic
832 evidence comes from simple vial drops—cavitation appeared within 30 μ s and drove antibody aggrega-
833 tion³¹⁵. Atomistic simulations corroborate these findings: while a planar shock compresses proteins
834 elastically, an asymmetric void collapse ejects a nano-jet that leaves the molecule partially unfolded
835 and aggregation-prone³¹⁶. To protect labile proteins against these one can limit pulse energy, de-
836 gas buffers or potentially add acoustic dampers; conversely, cavitation can be harnessed deliberately
837 for protein unfolding and aggregation, tissue ablation or sterilisation. These mechanisms must be
838 considered when evaluating the effects of intense EFs on proteins.

839 3.2 Indirect electrochemical effects of EF

840 3.2.1 pH change

841 Intense pulsed (or low-frequency) EFs can force Faradaic reactions at electrodes, driving steep local
842 pH shifts:

843 Within several ms pulses, when intense EF is applied driving direct-current, the anodic boundary
844 layer can acidify to low pH while the cathodic layer simultaneously alkalinises to high pH, provided
845 the rate of electrolysis outstrips the local buffer capacity³¹⁷. Such pH changes rapidly protonate or
846 de-protonate ionisable side chains, disrupting salt bridges, neutralising charge balance, and trigger-
847 ing unfolding or aggregation, see the review³¹⁸ on general pH dependence of protein stability. For
848 example, in electrospray ionisation capillaries acting as anodes, Konermann *et al.* detected >2-unit
849 pH drops that unfolded cytochrome C, evidenced by higher charge-state spectra; raising flow or alter-
850 ing grounding decreased electrolysis and preserved the fold³¹⁹. This demonstrates that apparent
851 EF effects may actually be hidden pH artefacts. Increasing buffer strength often increases electric
852 conductivity hence current, so H^+ / OH^- production scales up and the width of the pH front changes
853 only marginally³²⁰. Thus “more buffer” rarely solves the problem. The pH shifts can be minimized (i)
854 using short bipolar pulses, (ii) adding sacrificial or ion-exchange layers on electrodes³²¹, (iii) separa-
855 ting the sample via salt bridges³²², or accounted for by monitoring pH or applying matched chemical

controls. Electrode-driven pH excursions, not the EF itself, often compromise protein integrity under intense EFs. Proper pH monitoring and mitigation are essential before attributing structural changes to direct EF–protein interactions.

3.2.2 Reactive species generation

RXS (X = O,N,S,Cl,...) ³²³ can be produced by EF either faradaic reactions (always present at for resistive current at electrode-electrolyte interface) ³²⁴ or by extremely large EF if it leads to shockwaves, cavitation ^{310,312} and following sonochemistry. Principally, the consequent effect of RXS species on proteins is similar regardless of their origin. At anodic potentials, water oxidation yields •OH which diffuses or dimerises to H₂O₂; cathodic O₂ reduction gives O₂^{•-} ³²⁴. Cavitation adds pyrolytic •OH and •H, plus NO• in air-filled bubbles ³¹⁴. These species consequently produce secondary ROS/RNS that oxidise Met, Cys, Tyr, Lys and backbone α-carbons, raising carbonyl content, cross-linking dityrosine or fragmenting chains ^{325,326}. We recently showed ^{324,327} that BSA remained largely intact under microsecond PEF alone, whereas the addition of exogenous H₂O₂ markedly increased oxidation signals ³²⁴. This indicates that, for these pulse conditions, protein damage is dominated by indirect ROS chemistry (electrochemically generated) rather than by a direct EF-induced conformational disruption.

3.2.3 Bubble formation

Electrolysis, boiling hotspots and cavitation all inject gas–water interfaces. Proteins adsorb to the surfaces of stable bubbles, unfold as hydrophobic cores contact the gas phase and desorb as aggregation-prone species. Cryo-EM studies reveal ~80% denaturation of fatty-acid synthase at the air–water interface ³²⁸, while “do-not-drop” tests linked vial impact to bubble-induced protein particles via cavitation and radical chemistry ³¹⁵. In EF devices, anodic O₂ and cathodic H₂ bubbles combine pH extremes with interface stress, often leaving crusts of precipitated protein on electrodes. Degassing, pulse trains that allow gas purge, and low-level surfactants that shield interfaces are practical safeguards.

Each indirect pathway: heating, electro-hydrodynamic flows, shock-cavitation, pH drifts, ROS/RNS reactions and bubble interfaces – can appear simultaneously in a high-EF protocol. Disentangling them through temperature probes, pH indicators, radical scavengers, acoustic sensors, in situ imaging and spectroscopy enables rational process design, whether the goal is to dissect the mechanism of EF action or for biotechnological or industrial applications.

4 Discussion

4.1 EF strength and timescale: their scaling and (mis)match between simulations and experiments

In most of the works aiming to probe the direct effects of EF on proteins, the fields have to exceed certain threshold EF strength for the effect to manifest, see Fig. 16. In many cases, that limit would be EF strengths on the order of hundreds of MV/m, although the exact threshold for such effects depends very much on the protein systems and experimental conditions and goes down to 10 kV/m ¹²⁵. It is insightful in this context to consider the strength of EFs that occur naturally in cells and proteins. Typical membrane potentials across the cell membranes of eukaryotic cells are approximately 100 mV, which if one assumes a membrane thickness of about 4 nm ³²⁹ yields field strengths of up to tens of

896 MV/m. EFs inside the catalytic sites of enzymes reach EF strengths of GV/m and beyond^{34,41,222}.
897 Therefore, we do not focus on weak and ultra-weak EF (< 0.1 kV/m) effects, where direct effects
898 of EF on molecules are expected to be negligible compared to thermal electric noise. For this rea-
899 son, the weak electromagnetic field effects on biological systems present major controversies in the
900 bioelectromagnetic research and have been a focus of other reviews^{330–338}.

901 Both computational modeling and experimental studies consistently demonstrate the influence of
902 EFs on proteins, with clear evidence of translational and rotational motion, as well as strong indica-
903 tions of EF-induced changes in secondary, tertiary, and quaternary structures. However, a comparison
904 of EF strengths and timescales used in these two approaches (Tables 3 vs. 2) reveals substantial dis-
905 crepancies. MD simulations typically employ EF strengths that are significantly (often several orders
906 of magnitude) higher than those used in experiments, and they operate over much shorter timescales.
907 These differences arise from fundamental limitations inherent to molecular simulation methods. MD
908 simulations are restricted to nanosecond-to-microsecond timescales due to computational cost, which
909 necessitates the use of elevated field intensities to induce observable structural changes within such
910 brief periods. Furthermore, the systems modeled in MD are highly idealized: they are small in size
911 and lack real-world complexities such as dislocations, grain boundaries, impurities, and environmen-
912 tal heterogeneity (e.g., variable solvent conditions). The use of empirical interatomic potentials (force
913 fields), which approximate rather than fully capture quantum interactions, further constrains accu-
914 racy. Additionally, temperature control mechanisms such as thermostats may artificially suppress slow
915 conformational dynamics, further limiting the observable impact of low-intensity fields. As a result,
916 simulations conducted at experimentally realistic field strengths, but at significantly smaller durations,
917 frequently show only limited effects, such as electrophoretic motion, without substantial conforma-
918 tional changes. To overcome these limitations, MD simulations often rely on stronger EFs to accelerate
919 rare events—such as folding, unfolding, or large-scale domain reorientation—that would otherwise
920 occur over milliseconds or longer. This approach enables researchers to probe mechanisms of field-
921 induced structural change within accessible simulation windows. Thus, the application of higher EF
922 strengths in MD simulations, beyond those typically used in experimental settings, is a practical ne-
923 cessity driven by limitations in accessible timescales, system sizes, and the fidelity of current force
924 fields. Although the quantitative thresholds for structural changes observed in simulations may not
925 align directly with experimental values, the underlying mechanistic insights remain highly valuable.
926 Bridging this gap requires the integration of multiscale modeling approaches, the refinement of inter-
927 atomic potentials, and the development of scaling frameworks that enable a more accurate translation
928 of computational findings into experimentally relevant predictions.

929 From a purely academic perspective, one approach is to bring the experimental time scales to
930 the ones of simulation. That can be done using fast and ultra-fast spectroscopy techniques^{339,340} and
931 advanced ultra-fast single molecule or super-resolution imaging and microscopy techniques^{341,342}, see
932 Fig. 15 graphical overview of variety of systems used to expose the proteins to EF. For the advanced
933 techniques to serve the research on EF effects on proteins, it is necessary to integrate them with EF
934 exposure systems so that the effects can be analyzed in real time during the EF pulse and also shortly
935 after to match the short simulation time scales. Still, there will be a physical limit to the strength of an
936 EF that can be applied for a water-based protein sample for a given time before dielectric breakdown
937 occurs. Although the dielectric strength for distilled water (at 25 °C and normal atmospheric pressure)

is approximately 30 MV/m for a static (long duration) field, this threshold increases if the field acts only for a short time. For instance, small area and small gap systems can hold up to 100 MV/m up to 100 ns and up to 400 MV/m up to 20 ns³⁴³ and this threshold might depend on conductivity³⁴⁴.

However, for practical applications, one might need to use longer duration electric pulses and lower EF strength. In that case, the molecular modeling strategies should comply and extend the time scale to bridge to the experiment. This is possible either by increasing computational power or applying further coarse-grained approaches in the simulations^{345,346}, which will enable the analysis of either longer time scales or larger protein systems. Longer simulations will also be able to address the question of the reversibility of the EF-induced conformational and structural changes in proteins^{125,216,266,347,348}. To increase the match between molecular modelling predictions and experiments, a promising avenue in a different direction to coarse-grained simulations is to include electronic effects, which are absent in classical MD simulations with standard (non-polarizable) force fields. Including electronic effects can be done by employing polarizable force fields³⁴⁹ or even more accurate approximations using *ab initio* calculations^{350,351} - such effects contribute to the molecular polarization due to external EF and hence might influence the effects and their thresholds in simulations.

Theoretical considerations bringing together EF strength and time scales required for effects on proteins to take place have the ability to integrate the effects from molecular simulations and experiments. The classical work of EF effect on chemical reactivity of molecules, including proteins, from a thermodynamic perspective, is that from E. Neumann³⁵². We recently proposed a related theoretical approach on a single molecule level and verified its utility on EF-mediated dissociation of a kinesin protein from the microtubule (lattice of tubulin heterodimers)²²⁵. There, we quantified the time needed to detach the kinesin from tubulin in each simulation. To rationalise the observed dependence of kinesin-microtubule (MT) dissociation on EF strength, we recast the detachment process and its time-scale within Arrhenius framework assuming single energy barrier. While demonstrated on this single protein complex system, we believe that this approach could be used generally for any process where EF is acting to lower the energy barrier, hence modifying the rate of the process. In the absence of an applied EF, the rate (having units 1/s) is (for the particular case in our work²²⁵, it was the kinesin detachment rate from microtubule)

$$k_{\text{OFF}_0} = A \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_a}{k_B T}\right), \quad (1)$$

where A is a pre-exponential factor, ΔE_a the activation barrier, k_B the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. An external EF performs work on the protein system to effectively lower the barrier ΔE_a . Treating the EF as a force acting along the reaction coordinate leads to a modified Arrhenius expression^{353,354}

$$k_{\text{OFF}}(E) = A \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta E_a - E I_E}{k_B T}\right] = k_{\text{OFF}_0} \exp\left(\frac{I_E}{k_B T} E\right), \quad (2)$$

where E is the EF strength (e.g. in MV/m) and I_E (C · m) quantifies the coupling between the field and the reaction coordinate and has units of dipole (C.m) and it is denoted in literature as $\Delta\mu$ ²² or ΔM ³⁵² - change of a dipole moment between the two states (before and after the transition).

974 Expressing the rate in logarithmic form yields a linear relation

$$\ln k_{\text{OFF}}(E) = \ln k_{\text{OFF}0} + \frac{I_E}{k_B T} E, \quad (3)$$

975 which is a convenient form of equation: the slope directly reports on $I_E/(k_B T)$. We further pon-
976 dered about the physical origin of the interaction term I_E . While the the nature of I_E will be concep-
977 tually similar across proteins systems (related to charges and dipoles affected by EF in a particular
978 process), the magnitude I_E will be very much protein system and process specific. In the case of
979 our earlier work²²⁵, both torque on the kinesin/ β -tubulin dipoles and direct electrostatic work on
980 charged residues cooperate to lower ΔE_a , accelerating detachment at high EF strengths. As such,
981 Eq. (2) provides a compact quantitative framework for bridging the EF strength and time scales (via
982 rate) of a process and is broadly applicable to other molecular and protein systems subjected to EF.
983 Beyond structural descriptors, many studies now quantify EF effects directly in functional metrics
984 such as binding affinities, catalytic rates, transport fluxes, and assembly/disassembly kinetics, which
985 enables comparisons across systems and modalities. Examples span multi-fold changes in binding con-
986 stants¹⁷⁹, strong activity modulation in enzymes¹⁶⁷, and pronounced acceleration of motor-protein
987 detachment kinetics under intense fields²²⁵. Reporting calibrated local fields alongside such quan-
988 titative functional observables will be essential for translating mechanistic insights into predictive,
989 application-oriented design.

990 To provide an at-a-glance overview for non-specialists, Table 1 summarizes typical external-field
991 strengths and effective forcing timescales across common modalities in protein EF research.

992 To provide an at-a-glance overview for non-specialists, Table 1 summarizes typical external-field
993 strengths and forcing protocols across common modalities in protein EF research. For pulsed modal-
994 ities, we distinguish the single-pulse width τ_p from the cumulative “on-time” $\tau_{\text{on}} = N\tau_p$ (sum over N
995 pulses); the elapsed experiment time can be much longer due to interpulse gaps.

996 4.2 Solvent- and ion-mediated contributions: bridging direct and indirect effects

997 External EFs always act on proteins within a solvent/ion matrix; thus even ostensibly “direct” EF-
998 protein couplings are frequently mediated by the reorganization of hydration water and mobile ions.
999 In bulk water, molecular simulations show that static EFs induce pronounced anisotropy in structure
1000 and dynamics (hydrogen-bond kinetics, reorientation and translation)³⁵⁶, while oscillatory fields can
1001 drive non-equilibrium responses that depend on frequency and field amplitude³⁵⁷. At sufficiently
1002 strong fields, water can also exhibit enhanced proton-transfer/dissociation behavior and nontrivial
1003 thermodynamic (including entropic) contributions^{358,359}.

1004 These solvent responses feed back on proteins by (i) changing effective dielectric screening and
1005 local electrostatic potentials, (ii) modifying hydration-shell friction and thus rotational diffusion and
1006 conformational kinetics, (iii) reshaping ion atmospheres and interfacial double-layer dynamics (thereby
1007 enabling electroosmotic/ICEO flows), and (iv) providing chemical pathways for electrochemistry-
1008 driven ROS/RNS formation in electrode-based geometries. A unified perspective is therefore to treat
1009 observed protein responses as a superposition of intramolecular EF coupling and solvent-/interface-
1010 mediated contributions, with the relative weight determined by waveform, frequency, conductivity,
1011 and boundary conditions. This framework also helps rationalize why similar nominal E can yield

Table 1 Typical orders of magnitude of external electric-field strengths and forcing protocols across common modalities in protein EF research. For pulsed modalities we report the pulse width τ_p and the cumulative “on-time” $\tau_{\text{on}} = N\tau_p$ (sum over N pulses). Values are approximate and intended as guidance; specific implementations vary with geometry, conductivity, and waveform.

Modality	Typical E	Forcing protocol (τ_p , N , τ_{on})	Notes / dominant couplings
All-atom MD (uniform static / AC)	10 MV/m–10 GV/m	continuous (static/AC); $\tau_{\text{on}} \approx 50 \text{ ps}–5 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$	High E often used to access rare events on short trajectories; bulk periodic solvent, limited interfaces ^{79,138,181} .
EF-X in crystals (nanosecond pulses)	50–100 MV/m	$\tau_p \approx 50–500 \text{ ns}$; $N \approx 1$; $\tau_{\text{on}} \approx \tau_p$	Direct, ultrafast perturbation; can drive coordinated motions along functional modes ²² .
THz / mm-wave irradiation (pulsed or gated)	0.1 kV/m–100 MV/m	ultrafast: $\tau_p \approx 0.5–10 \text{ ps}$; gated trains: $\tau_p \sim 0.1–1 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$; $N \sim 10^5–10^8$; $\tau_{\text{on}} \sim 1 \text{ }\mu\text{s}–10 \text{ ms}$	Couples to collective modes; can be nonthermal or thermal depending on absorption and duty cycle (instantaneous E vs. duty) ^{24,25,163,177,293} .
Electrode-based PEF (solutions / cells)	0.1–10 MV/m	$\tau_p \approx 1 \text{ ns}–1 \text{ ms}$; $N \sim 10–10^4$; $\tau_{\text{on}} \sim 1 \text{ }\mu\text{s}–100 \text{ ms}$	EF direct effects are often mixed with Joule heating and electrode reactions; elapsed treatment time can be $\gg \tau_{\text{on}}$ ^{134,243,343,355} .
Low-frequency AC / DC (microfluidics, electrodes)	1 V/m–100 kV/m	continuous / sinusoidal: $\tau_{\text{on}} \approx 1 \text{ s}–\text{days}$ (period $\sim 1 \text{ }\mu\text{s}–1 \text{ s}$)	Electroosmosis/ICEO and electrohydrodynamic flows can dominate near interfaces at low f ^{165,173,304–306} .

different outcomes in simulations (periodic bulk solvent, no electrodes) versus experiments (finite cells with interfaces and electrochemical constraints) and it is therefore important to consider such differences when comparing results obtained under seemingly identical conditions.

4.3 Research at higher complexity scales: protein-containing biosystems and biosamples

There are classes of research works that observe the effects of EF on proteins in complex systems. While the complexity of the systems (cells, tissues, complex food matrices) makes it difficult to assess whether direct or indirect EF effects are in place or the effects were taking place indirectly through other non-protein biomolecular components or indirect EF effects, these works seem to share common effects at the level of proteins so we briefly review them here. In one class of the works, typically from food research and biotechnology^{51,54–57,59–63,241,360–364}, often the complex samples containing proteins (mostly enzymes) were exposed to EF. We excluded these studies from Table 2 in cases when the protein type and content of the protein-containing sample (intact or homogenized fruit, plant, or

meat tissue) is undefined or EF is used also for substantial thermal treatment, hence obscuring the mechanism of EF action. However, the results therein are relevant for research in the food industry and also provide an indication of and inspiration for research on the EF effects on proteins. The techniques employed to explore EF effects on proteins included native PAGE³⁶⁵, SDS-PAGE^{366,367}, UV absorption spectroscopy^{366,367}, intrinsic (Trp or Tyr) fluorescence^{368–371}, CD spectroscopy^{371,372}, FTIR spectroscopy^{366,373–375}, Raman spectroscopy³⁷⁶, accessible sulfhydryl group content determination^{176,365–367,371,372,377,378}, high-performance size-exclusion chromatography³⁷², high-performance liquid chromatography³⁶⁵, protein surface hydrophobicity assay^{367–369,377}, dynamic light scattering^{176,365,372,378,379}, turbidity analysis³⁶⁷, transmission electron microscopy³⁷⁹, viscosity measurement^{378,379}, and enzyme activity assay^{380–383}. The results in these studies align with those in Section 2 and Table 2: EF exerted effects on the conformational change^{366–369,371,375,376,378}, protein secondary structure^{366,371–375}, partial or complete protein unfolding^{367,370,371,375–377}, affected the enzymatic activity^{382,383}, aggregation^{176,365,367,375,378}, changed immunoreactivity³⁷¹ and rheological properties of the sample^{176,176,365,377,379}.

Another class of works focused on the analysis of (mostly pulsed) EF on proteins and their structure in cells. In such works, it was not possible to determine whether the effects of EF on the protein structures in the cells were direct or indirect (e.g., down-stream effects owing to plasma or internal membrane electroporation and change of intracellular ionic concentration or consequent cell swelling³⁸⁴). In these studies, most of the tools used to explore such effects were fluorescence-based microscopy techniques (epifluorescence, confocal), which enabled localization and visualization of the protein structures, such as cytoskeleton fibers. For instance, the effects of pulsed EF on cytoskeleton structures were explored in several works⁶⁵. It was found that a microtubule network was disrupted^{289,385–388} or more densely packed³⁸⁹ either immediately or with some delay after electric pulses were applied. A recent study demonstrated the possibility to remodel the MT cytoskeleton in cells without a complete de-polymerization phase³⁹⁰. Furthermore, the effects of a PEF were also observed on actin filaments³⁹¹ in plant cells and in animal cell cultures^{386,389,392–394}. In some studies^{395,396}, the finding that the presence of Ca²⁺ in the buffer was required to obtain the EF effect strongly indicated that the EF acted only indirectly on actin filaments through modification of calcium signaling.

These *in vivo* (i.e., in cells) observations of effects of EF on protein-based structures are biologically and biotechnologically significant, as they enable control of the cell fate with a physical EF handle. Although in most cases they can not provide a mechanistic understanding of the primary target of EF action, they provide inspiration for researchers to generate hypotheses for further *in vitro* research, such as in³⁹⁷.

4.4 Further outstanding questions for future research

4.4.1 How does protein structure affects the protein susceptibility to EF ?

Empirical evidence directly linking protein structure content to EF susceptibility is still sparse: beyond two atomistic studies^{68,184}, there is no systematic mapping across folds. These works tentatively suggest topology-dependent behavior (e.g., comparatively modest perturbations for some α -helical segments under oscillatory EFs versus strand orientation-dependent responses in β -sheets), but the limited protein set, simulation timescales, and model conditions preclude general conclusions. Paral-

lels with single-molecule pulling³⁹⁸ indicate that architecture governs responses to directed perturba- 1065
tions (α -helices “unzip,” β -sheets resist via shear), hinting that EFs—acting along charge distributions 1066
rather than through tensile loading, could produce analogous, structure-specific effects; however, such 1067
analogies must be drawn with care given the different coupling mechanisms and timescales. Resolving 1068
how protein structure affects EF susceptibility will require coordinated experiments and simulations 1069
across diverse folds (including intrinsically disordered regions), with controlled field strengths, orien- 1070
tations and waveforms (static, pulsed, oscillating), and orthogonal structural and functional readouts. 1071

4.4.2 What is the reversibility of the EF effects on proteins ? 1072

The reversibility of protein structural changes under EFs is only sparsely documented, with most 1073
reports scattered across disparate experimental and computational studies. Nonetheless, emerging 1074
evidence suggests that reversibility is possible below certain system-specific thresholds of field mag- 1075
nitude, exposure duration, and orientation, while exceeding these limits tends to yield irreversible 1076
outcomes. 1077

In early PEF work, ovalbumin exposed to 2.7–3.3 MV/m exhibited transient activation of sulfhydryl 1078
groups and minimal spectroscopic changes, with recovery of the native-like state over minutes to 1079
hours³⁹⁹, consistent with partial unfolding followed by refolding. In cytoskeletal systems, intense 1080
nanosecond pulses at 2 MV/m modulated tubulin conformation and *in vitro* microtubule assembly; 1081
recovery of repolymerization capacity after cold depolymerization was observed at modest pulse num- 1082
bers, while high-dose exposures led to incomplete restoration, indicating a graded shift from reversible 1083
to irreversible²¹. The recent study by Wang *et al.*¹⁸⁰ on soy protein isolates mapped a critical intensity 1084
near 1–1.5 MV/m, below which depolymerization and aggregation changes reversed within ~ 30 min, 1085
while at ≥ 2 MV/m reaggregation was stabilized by hydrophobic and disulfide crosslinks. 1086

Atomistic simulations extend these experimental findings, albeit in different range of EF strengths 1087
and timescales. Density functional theory/PCM calculations on model α -helices revealed a threshold 1088
near ≈ 2.6 GV/m for complete helix disruption when the EF is aligned with the helix dipole; impor- 1089
tantly, removing the field allowed the misfolded peptide to refold to near-native geometry, even in 1090
polar solvents⁴⁰⁰. Constant-field MD of lysozyme in the 0.5 GV/m range under static and oscillating 1091
conditions showed accelerated hydrogen-bond breakage/reformation cycles, largely reversible except 1092
for some persistent losses in solvent-exposed charged regions at specific driving frequencies⁴⁰¹. For 1093
ubiquitin, moderate fields ($\lesssim 0.5$ GV/m) induced reversible dipole reorientation and minor secondary- 1094
structure changes, while higher fields (1–2 GV/m) could still be reversible if switched off prior to 1095
overstretching¹⁴⁰. 1096

Analogies can be drawn—cautiously—from protein refolding after mechanical unfolding²²⁹, re- 1097
assembly of supramolecular protein complexes, and reversible disruption of peptide–peptide inter- 1098
faces. Across these contexts, reversibility hinges on perturbations that do not cross irreversible kinetic 1099
barriers such as extensive hydrophobic-core exposure or covalent bond scission. For EF perturbations, 1100
key determinants include field vector relative to the intrinsic protein dipole, temporal waveform, and 1101
structural context (e.g., solvent-exposed flexible tails versus buried secondary-structure cores). De- 1102
signing EF protocols that exploit such “safe windows” could enable reversible, on-demand modulation 1103
of protein structure and function. 1104

Across field modalities, the characteristic recovery time and dominant sources of irreversibility 1105

span many orders of magnitude. In EF-X, perturbations delivered on nanosecond timescales can drive reversible, collective motions in crystals without apparent structural degradation²². In sub-THz/THz irradiation, the primary solvent relaxation occurs on ps–ns timescales, suggesting that reversible modulation is plausible provided that the field does not trigger large-scale unfolding or chemical modification^{24,163}. By contrast, in electrode-based PEF experiments, irreversibility often originates from indirect pathways (Joule heating, pH gradients, ROS, and bubble interfaces), which act on ms–min timescales and can accumulate under repeated exposures. This is particularly relevant for emerging protein/peptide-based piezoelectric platforms⁴⁰², where longevity may be limited by cumulative electrochemical and hydration changes; mitigating strategies include minimizing duty cycle (an E^2 -weighted “dose”), using bipolar pulses, and isolating electrodes from the protein-containing volume²⁶⁶.

5 Conclusion

External electric fields (EFs) offer a powerful, reagent-free handle to perturb proteins and to modulate their interactions and function. Across the studies reviewed here, EFs couple directly to charged and dipolar groups, biasing rigid-body motion, reshaping intra- and inter-molecular electrostatics, and—when sufficiently strong or resonant with intrinsic motions—modifying secondary/tertiary/quaternary structure. In parallel, high-field protocols often introduce indirect electrophysical and electrochemical stresses—Joule heating, electrohydrodynamic flows, shock/cavitation, electrolysis-driven pH gradients, reactive oxygen/nitrogen species (ROS/RNS), and bubble interfaces—that can dominate the observed outcome if not controlled.

A central message is that “EF effects on proteins” should be interpreted as a competition between direct EF–protein coupling and solvent-/interface-mediated pathways. The balance is set by the field strength, waveform and frequency, exposure time (or duty cycle), and geometry (electrode-based vs. contactless), together with protein stability and solution conditions (conductivity, ionic strength, buffering capacity, redox environment). When indirect pathways are mitigated, reversible control becomes feasible: ultrafast nanosecond perturbations in EF-X can drive coordinated motions along functional modes²², while pulsed MV/m regimes and THz exposures can modulate binding, catalysis and supramolecular assembly on experimentally accessible timescales^{24,25,225}. When indirect stresses accumulate (heating, electrochemical byproducts, interface adsorption), irreversible unfolding and aggregation are more likely.

Preliminary design rules for EF-based protein control.

- **Match the field vector to the target degree of freedom.** Orientation and torque couple to the permanent dipole moment and charge distribution, while local polarization and bond-scale rearrangements couple to induced dipoles and heterogeneous internal electrostatics. Electro-optical experiments and modelling commonly place protein dipole moments in the $\sim 10^2$ – 10^3 D range, so fields of order 1–10 MV/m already give $\mu E \sim k_B T$ and can bias orientation, whereas remodeling tertiary interfaces, oligomer contacts, or buried secondary structure typically requires substantially larger effective fields and/or longer forcing, and is strongly direction-dependent^{22,81,113,116,225}.
- **Treat dose as a coupled strength–time problem.** For many indirect pathways (Joule/dielectric heating, electrolysis, electrode corrosion, electrothermal/electrohydrodynamic flows), the accumulated “damage” or energy deposition scales approximately with an E^2 -type integral over

the duty cycle (e.g. $\propto \int E^2(t) dt$ or $\propto \sigma E^2$ for Ohmic heating), so short pulses can access large peak fields while limiting bulk temperature rise and electrochemical accumulation^{294,299,403}. For *direct* EF-driven conformational/functional changes, however, the field–time trade-off can be much steeper: if the EF lowers an effective activation barrier, the response rate can follow an Arrhenius-like dependence $k(E) \approx k_0 \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta G^\ddagger(E)}{k_B T}\right]$, with $\Delta G^\ddagger(E) \simeq \Delta G_0^\ddagger - \Delta \mu^\ddagger E$ (or related forms), implying an *exponential* sensitivity to E ^{22,225,352–354}. For pulsed protocols, explicitly report both the single-pulse width τ_p and the cumulative on-time $\tau_{\text{on}} = N\tau_p$ (and also the total elapsed exposure time), because large- N pulse trains can have $\tau_{\text{on}} \ll$ elapsed time yet still produce substantial thermal/chemical dose.

- **Tune spectral content (frequency and waveform) to the target timescale, and to suppress unwanted interfacial physics.** Protein dynamics spans picoseconds to days, so efficient forcing requires matching the stimulus bandwidth to the relaxation time of the targeted coordinate; narrowband drives can preferentially address a chosen dynamical window, whereas fast-rise pulses are inherently broadband and can excite multiple dispersive processes in water and biomolecules^{77,220,404}. Frequency also selects which *macroscopic* couplings dominate near interfaces: at low frequencies (typically $\lesssim 10$ kHz) electrical-double-layer charging and induced-charge electroosmosis are strong, while at higher frequencies the double layer cannot follow and electroosmotic contributions diminish^{304–306}. In the GHz–THz range, coupling can shift toward fast polarization dynamics and collective modes; outcomes then depend critically on absorption and duty cycle (thermal vs. nonthermal regimes)^{24,177}.
- **Control the matrix chemistry and interfaces.** Buffer conductivity and thermal properties set Joule heating and electrothermal flows; buffer capacity sets pH excursions; electrode composition and dissolved oxygen/metal ions/peroxides set susceptibility to electrolysis, corrosion, and ROS/RNS chemistry. Use matched chemical controls (conductivity, buffering, scavengers), minimize direct electrode contact when possible (coatings, salt bridges), and manage polarity/pulse structure (e.g. bipolar or burst protocols) to separate direct EF effects from chemistry-driven artifacts^{317,319–324}.
- **Account for solvent-mediated thermodynamics and nonlinear dielectric response.** Strong static and oscillating fields can reorganize water structure/dynamics (dielectric saturation, anisotropy, altered hydrogen-bond statistics), changing entropic contributions and effective local fields that feed back on protein stability and kinetics^{356–359,404}. These solvent responses may also limit durability in repeated-use bioelectronic and piezoelectric protein/peptide platforms⁴⁰².
- **Validate “direct” EF mechanisms with orthogonal controls and quantitative modelling.** Because indirect pathways can mimic “nonthermal” effects, combine structural/functional readouts with monitoring of temperature, pH, and electrochemical/ROS markers, and report geometry, conductivity, waveform details, and local-field estimates (or EM/thermal simulations) to enable reproducibility and cross-modality comparison^{47,297–299,403}.

Looking forward, closing the gap between simulations and experiments will require multiscale modelling (including explicit interfaces and realistic conductivity), improved force fields for polariza-

1186 tion and charge transfer, and experimental platforms that deliver well-calibrated fields while simul-
1187 taneously reporting structural and functional observables. Such advances should enable EF protocols
1188 that are not generic denaturants but rather tunable physical stimuli for selective, reversible and sus-
1189 tainable control of protein function.

1190 Author contribution

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1214 Conflicts of interest

1215 There are no conflicts to declare.

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Fig. 1 An overview scheme of the physical effects of an EF on proteins as observed in molecular dynamics simulations (Table 3) and/or in experiments (Table 2). The blue shade denotes the protein status before and the orange color is the status of protein during or shortly after EF action. The EF acts by force on protein as an electrically charged particle by causing translational motion and via protein electric dipole causing rotational motion of a protein. A sufficiently strong EF causes (in a field strength increasing manner) changes in protein structure ranging from slight conformational changes to alteration and disruptions in tertiary and even secondary structure leading to protein size and shape changes and ultimately can lead to unfolding. In another, complementary perspective the EF modulates the free energy landscape of the protein. The structural changes then lead to the modulation of protein electrostatic, nanomechanical, dynamic and vibrational properties from the across all levels of protein organization. EF can also act (often in parallel with effects on single protein chain structure) on the interactions between proteins either causing aggregation (via partial unfolding), or disassembly of homotypic or heterotypic protein poly/multi/oligomers, eventually perturbing or enhancing interaction of proteins with non-peptide interaction partners. Ultimately, EF can disrupt, modulate or even enhance the function of proteins in their enzymatic, self-assembling roles or affecting photonic (such as fluorescence) or channeling properties.

Fig. 2 Protein rotation due to torque of EF on protein permanent dipole is one of the most straightforward yet underutilized effects. A) Tubulin protein in molecular dynamics simulation (water and ions not shown) in 100 MV/m EF aligns its dipole moment (orange arrow) with the EF vector (black arrow on the top) within a few nanoseconds. Based on our data from⁷⁸. B) ubiquitin in gas phase molecular dynamics simulation rotates to align its dipole moment with EF vector. Adapted with permission from⁷⁹. ©(2017) American Chemical Society. C) pulsed EF (0.4 MV/m, 25 μ s) induces birefringence of water solution of tubulins due to alignment of tubulin proteins with EF. Adapted with permission from⁸⁰. ©(1985) Elsevier. D) same experimental method as in C, (birefringence signal in mV), relaxation of esterase solutions after 2.46 MV/m EF pulse. Adapted with permission from⁸¹. ©(1996) Elsevier. E) Time evolution of dipole moment magnitude of ubiquitin from molecular dynamics simulation. Protein is initially positioned with its dipole moment vector antiparallel to EF vector, hence undergoes fast compression. Then the protein swiftly rotates in parallel with the increase of dipole moment magnitude. T_1 , T_2 , T_3 corresponds to time points when the dipole magnitude was 1 \times , 2 \times , 3 \times the initial magnitude, respectively. The thick line is the mean of the traces from individual MD simulations. Adapted with permissions from⁸². ©(2022) Wiley.

Fig. 3 Conformation and tertiary structure changes in proteins induced by intense EF. A) EFs induce global conformational changes in the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein. Shown are representative RMSD trajectories under various EF strengths and structural snapshots under EF of 10 MV/m at selected time points during and after field exposure. Adapted from¹²⁵. Springer Nature (2024), CC BY 4.0. B) Tertiary structure response of lysozyme to subTHz EF perturbation. Pathway B (THz-3h vs. GC-3h): 0.1 THz irradiation strengthens signals of core methyl groups (red spheres) while peripheral sites weaken (blue), indicating core tightening. Pathway C (HTC-3h vs. GC-3h): Mild heating to 31°C causes the inverse effect—core weakening and peripheral strengthening—suggesting cavity loosening. b Sub-THz radiation modifies lysozyme hydration. Schematic shows altered hydration 24 h post-irradiation. Fast, H-bond–broken water transitions to structured hydration (ochre) at the heterogeneous surface, promoting hydrophobic shielding and altered surface energetics. Adapted from²⁴. Springer Nature (2024), CC BY 4.0. C EF-driven conformational changes in pea protein after 25 ns of 1 MV/m MD simulated EF exposure. Adapted with permission from¹²⁶. ©(2023) Elsevier. D) EF effects on the LNX2PDZ2 protein (PDB ID: 2VWR) revealed by time-resolved X-ray crystallography (EF-X). a) Sampling of charged residues (highlighted in red) illustrates potential EF-responsive sites; the ligand is shown in yellow. b) In EF-X, protein crystals are subjected to an EF pulse of duration τ (pump), followed by X-ray probing (probe) to detect induced structural changes. c) Example of local rearrangements in hydrogen bonding visualized in the electron density map. Lower: Time evolution of EF-induced structural responses is mapped onto the protein’s tertiary structure using C α atom positions; color intensity reflects IADDAT (Integration of Absolute Difference Density Above Threshold) values. Adapted with permission from²². ©(2016) Springer Nature. E) Fluorescence spectra of α -amylase after PEF exposure show field-strength–dependent red shifts, indicating tertiary structural rearrangement. Adapted with permission from¹²⁷. ©(2021) Elsevier.

Fig. 4 EF-induced secondary structure transitions in proteins. A) Nanosecond PEF (nsPEF) unfold myoglobin (Mb), as seen by the sharp drop in α -helical content. The structural transition from folded to unfolded Mb correlates with the timing of the nsPEF exposure. Adapted with permissions from¹⁵⁹. ©(2013) American Chemical Society. B) Oscillating EFs (20 MHz) progressively disrupt the secondary structure of an A β -42 peptide fragment, leading to decomposition over 110 ns. Snapshots show the gradual destabilization from N- to C-terminal under directional field-induced force. Adapted from¹³³. CY BY 4 (2025) American Chemical Society. C) Time-resolved secondary structure evolution of β -casein under pulsed EF from MD simulations. Frame-by-frame analysis reveals EF-induced transitions from α -helix (pink) to coil (cyan) and other motifs. Adapted with permissions from¹⁶⁰. ©(2023) Elsevier. D) Circular dichroism spectra of ovalbumin show increased ellipticity and loss of α -helicity with rising PEF strength at characteristic wavelengths (209, 215, and 221 nm), indicating unfolding or loss of ordered structure. Adapted with permissions adapted from¹⁶¹. ©(2018) Elsevier. E) CD spectra of pepsin exposed to varying PEF treatments show field-strength-dependent loss of secondary structure, reflected in reduced relative retention of activity (RRA) and spectral shifts, compared with thermal denaturation. Adapted with permission from¹⁶². ©(2004) American Chemical Society.

Fig. 5 One of the most common effects seen in molecular dynamics simulations with EFs is protein unfolding. Here we show an example of extensive analysis from¹²³, where unfolding pathways of ubiquitin in EF were obtained. Adapted from⁴⁷. CC BY 3 (2021) Royal Society of Chemistry.

Fig. 6 EFs effects on protein energetics and free-energy landscape. A), C) Snapshots of the opening detail (1st trajectory of $-X$ 100 MV/m data): between alpha-tubulin 2 and 3 of a microtubule wall ring, see Figure 11 and⁴⁶. Time evolution of the binding energy contribution of six highly contributing selected amino acids. Mean values (thick line) and the standard deviation (shaded envelope) are from $N = 3$ trajectories. Adapted from with permission⁴⁶. ©(2021) Elsevier. B) Sampled free-energy landscape of the peptide chignolin (see inset for the structure) for (a1) zero field, (b1) oscillating field, and (c1) static field. Adapted from¹⁸¹ under CC BY 4. D) Principle component analysis comparison for the C- α of Thioredoxin: no field (blue), $E = 60$ MV/m (yellow), $E = 120$ MV/m (violet). Adapted from¹⁸² under CC BY 4. E) Potential of mean force (PMF) for the Cav2.1 channel with and without the presence of external THz fields (EF strength 0.6 GV/m) at different frequencies. The PMF here characterizes the capability of Ca^{2+} ions to pass through channel. The black dashed lines represent the position of each site. Site 1 (319Gly, 668Glu, 1460Gly, 1756Ala), Site 2 (318Glu, 667Glu, 1459Glu, 1755Glu), Site 3 (317Met, 666Gly, 1458Gly, 1754Gly), Site 4 (316Thr, 665Thr, 1457Thr, 1753Thr). Adapted with permissions from¹⁸³. ©(2025) Elsevier.

Fig. 7 Electric-field effects on lysozyme phase behaviour, nucleation, and crystal quality. (A) Left: Phase diagram of lysozyme in protein–salt concentration space with or without EF (1 kHz, 6 kV/m). Blue circles: homogeneous protein solution; orange crosses: crystals; pink circled crosses: metastable liquid–liquid phase separation (LLPS). Red dash-dotted lines and arrows mark the field-induced downward shift of the crystallization and LLPS boundaries. Right: growth of a single crystal, plotted as the normalized length versus time for field-off and field-on conditions. Adapted from¹⁹² under CC BY 4. (B) Results of 24 h nucleation assays under various AC fields. Red squares indicate conditions where crystals appeared; blue diamonds indicate no observable nuclei. Adapted with permission from¹⁹³. ©(2008) AIP Publishing. (C) Mechanistic model illustrating how lysozyme dimers (impurities) incorporate at step edges during growth, generating misoriented subgrains; an external field inhibits dimer incorporation, reducing misorientation and enlarging subgrain domains. Adapted with permission from¹⁹⁴. ©(2014) American Chemical Society. (D) Optical micrographs of hen-egg-white lysozyme crystals grown with NiCl_2 under (a) no field, (b) a 500 kHz AC field, and (c) a 1 MHz AC field. Adapted with permission from¹⁹⁵. ©(2009) American Chemical Society.

Fig. 8 EF effects on local electrostatic properties of proteins and on protein dipole moment. A) 2D maps of the local electrostatic field distribution around the active site of SOD1. The maps show EF shifts on the representative planes π' (top row) and π'' (bottom row) due to monopolar nsPEF pulse (left) and bipolar one (right). Both signals alter the electrostatic map around the central copper ion, with monopolar pulse producing localized changes and bipolar pulse resulting in a more diffuse and uniform distribution, suggesting possible rotation of specific protein residues and charge redistribution under the applied field. Adapted from²¹⁶ under CC BY 4. B) Average x -component of the dipole moment of hen egg-white lysozyme (HEWL) under different EF conditions, computed across multiple simulation replicates. Adapted from¹⁸¹ under CC BY 4. C) Time evolution of the dipole moment magnitude of kinesin under five different EF conditions: no field (black), +100 MV/m along the X axis (red), -100 MV/m along the X axis (magenta), +100 MV/m along the Y axis (blue), and -100 MV/m along the Y axis (cyan). The EF is applied continuously for the entire duration of the molecular dynamics simulations. Solid lines represent the mean dipole magnitude, and the shaded regions indicate the standard deviation computed from $N = 3$ independent replicates. Insets show kinesin bound to a tubulin protofilament at the end of the simulation; black arrows denote the kinesin dipole vector, and colored arrows indicate the direction of the applied EF, using the same color scheme as the main plot. Adapted from²¹⁷ - CC BY. D) Representative structures of the chignolin peptide and surrounding hydration layers under applied EFs of (c) 0.7 GV/m and (d) 0.7 MV/m. Dipole moment vectors of the peptide and water molecules are shown as yellow and green arrows, respectively. The directions of the applied electric E and magnetic B fields are indicated with arrows. Adapted with permission from¹⁵³. ©(2016) AIP Publishing.

Fig. 9 EFs affects protein-protein interactions. A) kinesin motor domain on a segment of a microtubule is detached within a few ns by 100 MV/m EF in MD simulation. Adapted with permission from²²⁵. ©(2023) Elsevier, B) EF disassembles protein isolate complexes in MD simulation which is corroborated by increase of surface hydrophobicity in experiment (PEF firing frequency 1000 Hz, bipolar square wave: 40 μ s pulse, 200 μ s gap, 40 opposite polarity pulse, N=25 pulses) as probed by ANS fluorescence – both effects are EF strength-dependent. Adapted with permission from¹⁸⁰. ©(2024) Elsevier, C) Transmission electron microscopy evidences that EF (2+2 μ s bipolar pulses, 1 MV/m, firing frequency 2 kHz) causes disassembly of ferritin cage-like structures. Adapted with permission from¹⁴¹. ©(2021) Elsevier, D) 120 MV/m (1 ns pulse width, 1.7 Hz firing rate, N=1,000 pulses) pulsed EF promotes degradation of transthyretin aggregates. Adapted from²²⁶ - CC BY 4, E) Transmission electron microscopy images of human serum albumin fibrillar solutions: (a) without applied EF, and (b) after exposure to an EF of approximately 8 MV/m for 10 min. Adapted with permission from²²⁷. ©(2014) IOP, F) Turbidity, reporting protein aggregation, of ovomucin-depleted egg white solutions (10% w/w, pH 4–9) after PEF treatment at varying EF strengths, while maintaining a constant specific energy input $W_{spec} = 713$ kJ/kg. Adapted with permission from²²⁸. ©(2017) Elsevier.

Fig. 10 EF can also affect highly ordered protein structures, such as cytoskeleton protein polymers - microtubules. A) A schematic mechanism of EF action on microtubule, where the opening of the microtubule wall occurs due to action on dipoles of individual tubulin subunits B) snapshots from a representative MD simulation. Adapted with permission from⁴⁶. ©(2021) Elsevier.

Fig. 11 Imaging of EF effects on protein fibers: A) AFM imaging of the effects of pulse electric treatments of fiber-forming proteins. Sup35NM amyloid fibrils before and after PEF treatment (2 MV/m, 10 pulses, 1 ms pulse duration, 1 Hz firing frequency) - adapted from²³⁸ - CC BY 4. B) Control sample of self-assembled tubulin and the self-assembly from a tubulin treated by PEF (2 MV/m, 800 pulses, 10 ns pulse duration, 1 Hz firing frequency) - adapted with permission from²¹. ©(2019) Wiley. C) Intense picosecond (subTHz) electric pulses cause microtubule fragmentation (40.9 MV/m, 1 ps pulse duration, 1 kHz firing frequency). Here we show a time dependence of this process captured using fluorescence microscopy - adapted from²⁵ - Open Access license of The Optical Society/OPTICA.

Fig. 12 Protein-ligand interactions modified by EF. A) In PEF-treated (1 MV/m, 40 μ s pulse, firing frequency 1 kHz, N=20 pulses) pea protein isolate, the ligand (EGCG - epigallocatechin-3-gallate) occupies two high-affinity pockets (sites 1–2; $\Delta G = -9.1 / -9.0$ kcal mol⁻¹), expanding the total docking sites (obtained from molecular modeling) from four in control structure (no EF - not shown) to ten and increasing hydrophobic contacts from five to twelve through newly exposed residues such as Pro⁴⁵⁷ and Trp¹²⁹. Adapted with permission from¹²⁶. ©(2023) Elsevier. B) Schematic representation of the relationship between the curcumin-binding capacity and structural properties of BSA after PEF treatment. Photos: Visual inspection of free curcumin solution (left), BSA curcumin complex solution (middle) and PEF-treated BSA curcumin complex solution (right). Adapted with permission from¹⁷⁹. ©(2022) Elsevier. C) Snapshots of the 5-HT_{1A}-serotonin complex at 600 ns in no EF, 10 MV/m EF, and 30 MV/m EF, Serotonin is shown as sticks. Overlay of 5-HT_{1A} receptor structures from no EF (pink) and 30 MV/m EF system (yellow) MD simulations, spotlighting the conformational shift at the D^{3.32}-Y^{7.53} lock. Adapted with permission from¹³⁵. ©(2025) Elsevier. D) Relative intrinsic fluorescence quenching of α -amylase/pectin complexes after PEF treatment. The ordinate shows the fractional decrease in fluorescence, $(F_0 - F)/F_0$, while the abscissa lists the mass ratios of α -amylase to pectin (R32:1, R4:1, R1:1). PEF-treated samples (red circles) exhibit markedly greater quenching than non-treated controls (black squares), data represent mean \pm SD (n = 3). Structure of α -amylase. Adapted with permission from¹⁶⁷ ©(2020) Elsevier. with permission.

Fig. 13 EF effect on proteins' enzymatic function. A) Inactivation of horseradish peroxidase (HRP) exposed to EF strengths varying from 0.5 to 2.5 MV/m with 207 pulses during storage at 4 °C, respectively (measured immediately, 24 h, or 48 h after PEF treatment). The treatment temperature did not exceed 40 °C. Adapted with permission from²⁴². ©(2005) Elsevier. B) Inactivation of pepsin by PEF. The width and total treatment time were 2 μ s (bipolar pulses) and 126 μ s, respectively. The media are 7.5 mM HCl with a pH of 2.0 and an electrical conductivity of 0.391 S/m, and a water–phosphate–acetate mixture with a pH of 3.8 and an electrical conductivity of 0.345 S/m. Adapted with permission from¹⁶². ©(2004) American Chemical Society. C) The relative activity of CPG2 after nsEP exposure; relative activity (%) as a function of total exposure time t (s). * $p < 0.05$. Adapted with permission from²⁴³. ©(2015) Elsevier. D) Changes in the enzyme activity of alcalase after PEF treatment for different storage times. Data were expressed as the mean \pm SD, $n = 3$. a, b, c indicated that the enzymatic activity of alcalase was significantly different ($p < 0.05$). The docking model between a substrate (casein) and the alcalase molecule was generated by MD simulations under EF strengths of 0 and 1 MV/m. Figures (A, B, C, and D) are the docking results of alcalase molecules produced by MD simulation. Adapted with permission from²⁴⁴. ©(2022) Elsevier. E) Left: Effect of PEF treatment (pulse width, 2.5 μ s; frequency, 1128 Hz) at different EF intensities on the enzymatic activity of α -amylase (0.2 mM phosphate buffer, pH 6.0; enzyme concentration, 23 U/mL). Error bars represent standard deviation. The different letters mean the data of two samples are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Right: Optimum temperature (a) and pH (b) of α -amylase (enzyme concentration, 23 U/mL) with and without PEF treatment. PEF treatment: EF strength, 1.5 MV/m; flow rate, 100 mL/min; pulse width, 2.5 μ s; frequency, 1128 Hz. Error bars represent standard deviation. Enzyme activity at the optimum temperature or pH is considered 100%. Adapted with permission from²⁴⁵. ©(2016) Springer Nature.

Fig. 14 EF effect on membrane protein function. A) Structure of the voltage-gated ion channels (VGICs); progression of the radius of complex pores generated by the increasing applied EF. Adapted with permission from²⁶⁶. ©(2020) Elsevier. B) The Michaelis Mentin Enzyme will behave like a Brownian motor. The E_1 to E_2 transition can be induced by an applied EF. Adapted with permission from²⁶⁷. ©(2003) Association of Asia Pacific Physical Societies. C) Central intraprotein electropore; evolution of the electropore's shape during the simulation with applied EF. Adapted from²⁶⁸ - CC BY. D) Conduction through an endogenous channel; Approximate schematic of the electropore-channel radial shape. Adapted with permission from²⁶³. ©(2019) Royal Society of Chemistry. E) Depiction of layout of AQP4 and osmotic permeability static-field pulses applied at various EF strengths V/A. Adapted from²⁶¹ - CC BY.

Fig. 15 Exposure systems delivering EF to protein samples categorized according to the EF frequency range, bandwidth, observation capabilities *under operando*, and sample handling. Frequency range: *DC–low frequency*—electrode configurations that impose static or slowly varying fields on proteins, often in capacitor-like arrangement or as a coplanar electrodes, such as in²⁸⁶ - reproduced with permission, ©(2005) AIP publishing; *RF–microwave*—cells that expose samples to radio-frequency or microwave range signals usually employing transmission lines or waveguides, example from²² - reproduced with permission, ©(2016) Springer Nature; *Millimetre-wave/terahertz*—quasi-optical platforms that illuminate proteins with high-frequency EF, as in, e.g.,²⁵, adapted with permission from © Optical Society of America. Bandwidth: *Broadband, pulsed* - often transmission-line-based geometries for delivering nanosecond–microsecond field pulses with wide spectral content, such as in²⁸⁹, with permission; *Narrow-band, single frequency*—resonator or waveguide, or for low-frequencies even a simple capacitor assemblies, providing monochromatic excitation at a selected frequency, e.g.²⁹⁰ - reproduced under CC BY 4. Under-operando observation: *None*—closed reactors for bulk treatment without real-time monitoring, e.g.²²⁶ - reproduced under CC BY 4. *Spectroscopies*—field-delivery setups compatible with simultaneous optical, vibrational, or electronic probes such as in²⁹¹ - adapted with permission from IEEE (©2024); *Imaging*—transparent or open-access devices that enable concurrent microscopic visualisation, such as in²⁹² - adapted under CC BY 4. Sample handling: *Batch reactor*—static chambers in which the sample remains stationary during exposure¹⁶³ - adapted under CC BY 4; *Through-flow*—flow-through reactors allowing continuous processing under field stimulation and in-line probing²⁹³ - adapted under CC BY 4.

Fig. 16 Primary EF effects on proteins depend on EF strength E and protein structure. Geometrical direction of effects is consistent with the fact that EF vector is pointing from left to right. Protein always undergoes translation (electrophoretic force) as long as it has non-zero effective electric charge Q . Rotational force is also acting on protein proportional to the dipole moment p of the protein (blue arrow). Translation and rotation effects of EF on whole proteins (rigid body motions) are taking place at any field strength values. When the torque magnitude $T = E \cdot p$ significantly exceeds the energy due to rotational thermal motion (kT), the rotation becomes deterministic. In a multimeric protein complex, the translational force and rotation force due to EF act also on the local charges Q_L and dipoles, respectively, of individual subunits. If the EF force is higher than some threshold force, (i.e. interaction energy between EF and charges and dipoles and overcomes binding energy (E_B) between the monomer), it can cause disassembly of the complex, hence disrupting the quaternary structure. Within a protein, EF effects on the local charges and dipoles can cause deformation of the protein and affecting tertiary structure. Similarly, EF can affect the secondary structure and very high EF strength can lead to protein partial unfolding and denaturation. One has to keep in mind that the real picture is statistical: the thresholds are not sharp since EF changes the probability of events.

Table 2 Proteins in electric fields: experimental studies meeting the criteria for well-defined electric field exposure parameters, isolated protein samples, iso-thermal conditions, and confirmed protein identity. NR = Not Reported. If EF strength was not report, we either calculated it from available information, where possible, or we provide other closest related quantity

Protein [Reference]F	EF strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
alcohol dehydrogenase ⁴⁰⁵	0, 1.2–2.8 MV/m	40 μ s (bipolar square wave, details N.D.)	1 kHz	75 (calculated from effective treatment time 3 ms)	enzymatic activity assay, FTIR, CD, TRP/TYR fluorescence, UV-absorption, SDS-PAGE	secondary structure, tertiary structure, enzymatic activity	10 - 35°C
α -amylase ²⁴⁵	0 – 5 MV/m	2.5 – 20 μ s	1 – 10 kHz	80 pulses	enzyme activity assay, CD, Trp fluorescence	enzymatic activity (increased/decreased); structural: secondary structure (increase of α -helices and turns, decrease of β -sheets), tertiary structure (increase in Trp fluorescence)	25°C
α -amylase ²⁴⁶	100 V/m	continuous sine wave	1 Hz to 1 MHz	250 sec	enzyme activity assay	enzymatic activity (increased at lower frequencies)	60°C
α -amylase ¹²⁷	0.25 – 1.25 MV/m	10 μ s	1 – 30 Hz	40 min	enzyme activity assay, UV-absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy	enzymatic activity (reduced); structural: conformation change near the tryptophan residues	50°C
α -amylase/-pectin complexes ¹⁶⁷	0 – 2 MV/m	bipolar 40 μ s pulses	1 kHz	1.02 (2.03) ms	enzyme activity assay, DLS and zeta-potential, intrinsic fluorescence, FTIR, DSC, confocal light scanning microscopy (CLSM), SEM	enzymatic activity (decreased); structural: secondary structure (decrease of α -helices and increase of β -sheets), polarity of tryptophan microenvironment, charge redistribution, and strengthen of protein-polysaccharide association	30 \pm 0.5°C
α -amylase, lysozyme, lipase, peroxidase, alkaline phosphatase, polyphenol oxidase, glucose oxidase ²⁴⁹	1.3 – 8.7 MV/m	2 μ s	0.5 Hz	30 and 100 pulses at 2s pulse period	enzyme activity assays	enzymatic activity was reduced either vastly (lipase, glucose oxidase, and heat-stable α -amylase), moderately (peroxidase and polyphenol oxidase), or slightly (alkaline phosphatase)	20°C
β - lactoglobulin (β -lg) ⁴⁰⁶	1.25 MV/m	2 ms	0.07 Hz	1 – 10 pulses	DSC, SDS-PAGE, TEM	thermal stability was greatly reduced; the gelation rate was enhanced; structural: denaturation, aggregation	4 – 35°C
β - lactoglobulin (β -lg) ⁴⁰⁷	800 W	continuous irradiation	2.45GHz	5 s	polarimeter	enhanced kinetics of the folding and denaturation processes	4 – 44°C
β - lactoglobulin (β -lg) ²⁵²	up to 4.10 ⁵ kW	10 μ s	1 Hz	1 and 10 min (30 and 300 pulses)	OPA assay, determination of the kinetic parameters, CD	the tryptic and chymotryptic hydrolysis was significantly improved, the catalytic efficiency was improved; structural: electrical pretreatments induced changes in the three-dimensional structure of the protein bringing it to a transient or a pseudounfolded state	37 and 85°C
β -lg ¹⁷⁸	0-1 kV/m	NR	50 Hz – 1 MHz	NR	CD, Trp fluorescence, ANS fluorescence, quenching analysis-retinol	secondary structure (increase of random coil fraction, decrease of β -sheets); tertiary structure:(unfolding, increased of Trp fluorescence, higher affinity of hydrophobic compounds when exposed to higher temperatures); higher affinity with retinol (especially at lower frequencies)	20–95°C
actin ²³⁶	0.46 THz radiation with an energy dose of 5.7 mJ/cm ²	10 ms	1 Hz	1200 pulses (20 min duration of experiment)	polymerization assay, fluorescence microscopy	activation of the elongation phase of actin polymerization	25°C
alkaline phosphatase (AP), antidinitrophenyl(ar DNP) with its antigen ¹⁶⁴	0.08 W/m ²	continuous irradiation	100 GHz	1 – 2 hr.	enzyme activity and kinetics assay	AP: irradiation may lead to other structural alterations of the enzyme that impose conformational changes affecting the turnover of the enzyme, thereby reducing the number of active enzyme molecule in the solution, anti-DNP: no effects	25°C
amyloid- β (A β) ¹⁷⁷	0.73 mW/cm ² [E=234 V/m]	2 ms	repetition rate 100 kHz (34.88 THz)	NR	ThT fluorescence binding assay, FTIR	the aggregation speed ratio decreased to approximately 80%; the THz wave at 34.88 THz significantly slowed down the fibrotic progression; secondary structure (the structure of β -sheets were transforming to a looser structure with more coil and bend regions)	37°C

Continued on next page

Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
amyloidogenic fragment (1-27) and non-amyloidogenic fragment ⁴⁰⁸	177 V/m (calculated from spatial dose 150 mJ/cm ² and duty cycle)	1 ms	5 Hz	up to 30 min	scanning electron microscopy, Thioflavin T fluorescence, bright field microscopy (congo-red staining), synchrotron-radiation IR micro-spectroscopy	fibril aggregation of the peptides, increased formation of β -sheets. The effect present in amyloidogenic sequence, not in non-amyloidogenic ones. Equivalent heating did not cause fibril formation	27–30°C
citrate synthase- α -crystallin ⁴⁰⁹	1.443 kV/m (calculated from average SAR 4.85 kW/kg, assuming water as the material)	10, 15, and 20 s	2.45 GHz	continuous irradiation (as a characterized artifact the MW EF peaked by 3–8-fold above average amplitude each 50 Hz)	surface plasmon resonance	unfolding occurred at significantly lower temperatures	25°C, 29.5–44°C
BSA ¹⁷⁹	0, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5 and 3 MV/m	40 μ s	1 kHz	0.34 - 1.02 ms	fluorescence spectroscopy (fluorescence quenching, intrinsic fluorescence), CD, zeta potential, UV-absorption, ANS fluorescence, Ellman's assay, BSA/PBSA-curcumin binding affinity assays	moderate PEF treatment induce the partial unfolding of BSA, exposing more hydrophobic cavities, thereby facilitating the non-covalent binding of curcumin to protein (surface SH content was increased as well); however rigorous PEF treatment conditions caused BSA aggregation and weakened the binding ability of BSA to curcumin (increase of intermolecular disulphide interactions, excessive exposure of hydrophobic groups - hydrophobic collapse); secondary structure (decrease of α -helix structures, increase of β -sheet, β -coil and random coil content)	\leq 30°C
BSA ²⁴⁰	0, 0.5, 1 and 1.5 MV/m	20 μ s	1000 Hz	15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45 min.	SDS-PAGE, CD, attenuated total reflectance-FTIR, intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, UV-absorption, ANS fluorescence, Ellman's assay, DLS and zeta potential	the polarization effect of PEF enhanced the emulsifying properties of BSA-glucose conjugates by accelerating the glycation reaction, while the ionization effect significantly suppressed the browning; secondary structure (decrease of α -helix content, increase of β -sheet, β -coil and random coil content); tertiary structure: unfolding	90°C
BSA ²⁴¹	0.35, 0.45, 0.57, 0.81 MV/m	50 μ s	NR	10 pulses	DLS, CLSM, ANS fluorescence, DSC, intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy	At lower electric field strengths (0.35–0.57 MV/m), PEF treatment improved the browning intensity, the protein solubility and the grafting degree, and reduced the particle sizes, the fluorescence intensity and surface hydrophobicity of BSA/starch conjugates. At a higher electric field strength (> 0.57 MV/m), BSA/starch conjugates exhibited decreased protein solubility, grafting degree, and particle size increase	22.5–25.8°C
BSA and bovine insulin ⁴¹⁰	15-20 mW/kg, 0.5 W	–	1.0 GHz	3 to 48 h.	light scattering measurement, TEM, thioflavin T (ThT) assay	BSA: aggregate formation; bovine insulin: amyloid fibril formation	BSA: 25 to 45°C, bovine insulin: 60°C
BSA, microtubules ²⁹³	156 V/m (from 6.5 mW/cm ² beam power density)	CW	500 GHz radiation	0.4 s irradiation time	SAXS	No structural changes	NR
BSA, microtubules ²⁹³	1.8 MV/m	600 fs	100 MHz pulse repetition rate, effective irradiation spectrum 0.1 to 6.0 THz	0.2–0.4 s	SAXS	No structural changes	NR, temperature rise due irradiation <0.12°C
BSA lyophilized ²³⁹	5 – 20 mW (only laser power value was provided)	NR	3.6 THz	60 min. irradiation time	CD, UV-absorption, Trp fluorescence	conformational changes - secondary structure (changes the intensities of characteristic bands in UV absorption and CD spectra); modification of its functional characteristics - ligand binding parameters; As a ligand is added to the treated protein solution, the fluorescence quenching is observed	NR

Continued on next page

Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
BSA, lysozyme ¹⁶⁵	78, 150, 300 and 500 V/m	NR	10 and 500 Hz	3 hrs.	CD, intrinsic (Trp) fluorescence	the tertiary structure of both lysozyme and BSA was affected, the secondary structure was perturbed in lysozyme (decrease of α -helices and increase of β -sheets); the electric force applied during EF exposure was significant to perturb hydrogen bonds stabilizing the native structure of both proteins	22.7°C to 24.2°C
carboxypeptidase-G2 (CPG2) ²⁴³	1 MV/m	8, 16, 24 ns	10 Hz	20, 40, 60, 90, 120, 180 or 240 s	enzyme activity assay, SEC, reverse phase-HPLC, SDS-PAGE, MS and CD, inductively coupled plasma-MS	enzymatic activity (decreased)	NR
cytochrome c, myoglobin, trypsin ⁴¹¹	28-130 V/m	NR	NR	~ 90 min.	intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, attenuated total reflection infrared (ATR-IR), UV-VIS absorption, ThT fluorescence, CD, SEM	secondary- (both the α -helix and β -sheet content decreased) and tertiary structure unfolding; amorphous aggregation	25°C
286,288	1–10 MV/m	static field	-	-	intrinsic (TRP) fluorescence spectroscopy	change (decrease) of fluorescence intensity	20°C
ovomucin ²²⁸	70–170 kV/m	20 μ s	300 Hz	NR	SDS-PAGE, turbidimetry	aggregation	below 50°C
elastin ¹⁷³	12 and 20 kV/m	continuous exposure	continuous exposure	more than 5 days	DLS and zeta-potential, field emission-SEM, FTIR and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy	conformational changes in the secondary structure (increase of α -helices and decrease of β -sheets and turns); unfolding, denaturation and the size of the aggregates were reduced	RT
(enhanced) green fluorescent protein (EGFP) ²⁸⁴	250 mW	continuous microwave irradiation (100ps)	9.5 GHz	≈4.5 min.	fluorescence emission anisotropy	microwave irradiation affects polarization of the EGFP fluorescence	9.7–12.5 K
ferritin ¹⁴¹	1, 2, 3 or 4 MV/m	-	2000 Hz	-	CD, intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, cold field emission-SEM, TEM	secondary structure: as the electric field intensity increased, the α -helix content shown a trend of first decreasing and then increasing, and the β -sheet content trend was the opposite; tertiary structure: partial unfolding, decrease in the stability; reversible self-assembly; aggregation (the solubility of ferritin decreased with increasing exposure of hydrophobic groups - breakage of hydrogen bonds and the transformation of SS bridges)	RT
green fluorescent protein (GFPuv5) ²⁸³	50 and 70 MV/m	~60 ps	40 Hz	30 ms	electric field modulation spectroscopy	field-induced quenching of the fluorescence was observed, changes in the fluorescence decay profile - decrease in the fluorescence lifetime	RT
horseradish peroxidase (HRP) ²⁴²	0.5 – 2.5 MV/m	1.5 μ s	10 Hz	207 – 1242 pulses	enzyme activity assay, CD, intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy	enzymatic activity (decreased); secondary structure (decrease of α -helix content); tertiary structure (intrinsic fluorescence intensity increased)	below 40°C
human serum albumin (HSA) fibrils ²²⁷	0–23 MV/m	static field	-	10 min	ThT fluorescence, CD, FTIR spectroscopy, TEM, fluorescence microscopy	secondary structure (decrease of β -sheet content), the initial propagation of the fibrils was followed by the disintegration of the fibrillar network into smaller aggregates	RT
HSA fibrils ²³⁵	~8 MV/m	continuous exposure	5 to 100 Hz	1 – 6 min.	ThT fluorescence, CD, turbidimetry, DLS, FTIR spectroscopy, fluorescence microscopy, high resolution-TEM	an initial fibrillar growth was followed by the destruction of amyloid fibrils into smaller aggregates; secondary structure (reduction of β -sheets, increase of α -helix, β -turns and random structure content)	25±0.5°C
luciferase ⁴¹²	~ 0.75 MV/m	-	100 kHz continuous sine wave	EF 5 × 100 s ON and OFF, for signal integration	enzymatic assay, spectrometer	decreased luciferase activity	22°C
WT/A4V SOD1 ⁴¹³	25 kV/m	-	DC (via saltbridge, 14–18 μ A)	2–30 min	electrophoresis, UV-VIS spectroscopy	A4V Zn4-SOD1 monomerized and partially unfolded	15°C cooling of the capillary
lysozyme ⁴¹⁴	3.5 MV/m	bipolar square: positive 2 μ s, 20 μ s gap, negative 2 μ s	-	300, 600, 900, 1200 μ s	activity assay, CD, micro-Raman spectroscopy	activity of lysozyme decreased, changes in the secondary (loss of α -helices increase β sheets and random coil) and tertiary structure (transition of S-S conformation)	max 20°C

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Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
lysozyme ⁴¹⁵	3.5 MV/m	bipolar: positive 2 μ s, 15 μ s gap, negative 2 μ s	1 kHz	total exposure 300, 600, 900, 1200 μ s	lysozyme activity assay, aggregation analysis, sulfhydryl groups analysis, surface hydrophobicity analysis, Fluorescence analysis, circular dichroism	activity of lysozyme decreased-irreversible, aggregation effect only for 1200 μ s exhibition, increasing number of accessible sulfhydryl groups (cleavage of the disulfide bonds), hydrophobicity increased with subsequently hydrophobic collapse for longer EF exhibition then 600 μ s, increasing intensity in fluorescence spectra and red shifts after EF (changes in tertiary structure), changes in secondary structure (loss of α -helices)	55°C
lysozyme ⁴¹⁶	3.5 MV/m	2 μ s	1000 Hz	total exposure 300, 600, 900, 1200 μ s	activity assay, ANS-binding fluorescence, intrinsic fluorescence spectra, CD	decreasing activity of lysozyme, hydrophobicity increased with subsequently hydrophobic collapse for longer EF exhibition 1200 μ s, increases of fluorescent emission intensity and red shifts, changes in tertiary structures according to Near-UV CD analysis, conformational changes in secondary structure (loss of α -helices)	$\leq 60^\circ\text{C}$
lysozyme (crystal) ⁴¹⁷	65 mW/cm ² (490 V/m)	25 ms	0.4 THz	effect studied expected within a single pulse	structural analysis, x-ray crystallography	electron density changes - consistent with a subtle longitudinal compression of the α -helix	Lower than 25°C
lysozyme ²⁴	0.15 kV/m	0.8 μ s pulse filled 0.1 THz pulses	10 kHz	10 min	microwave dielectric relaxation spectroscopy, NMR	decrease the dielectric permittivity, Irradiation probably enhances hydration water with reduced mobility and more H-bonds,	25°C
hen egg-white lysozyme (HEWL) ⁴¹⁸	0, 1–2 MV/m (1 M for H ₂ O hydration; 2 MV/m for D ₂ O hydration)	static, N.A.	-	continuous during QENS (quasi-elastic neutron scattering acquisition (duration N.D.))	incoherent QENS (BASIS; $\Delta E \approx 3.5 \mu\text{eV}$; $Q = 0.3\text{--}1.1 \text{ 1/\AA}$)	No measurable change in protein dynamics (up to 2 MV/m) or hydration-water relaxation times (1 MV/m); authors suggest threshold $E_c \sim 2\text{--}3 \text{ MV/m}$ (breakdown-limited)	210–270 K
lysozyme, albumin and urease ⁴¹⁹	10, 15, 20, 25, 30 MV/m	5 ns	3 Hz	500 pulses	SDS–PAGE, Native–PAGE, enzyme activity assay	lysozyme and albumin without effect, urease: trimer and dimer shifted downward from 250 kV/cm in SDS–PAGE (quaternary and tertiary structure disruption), decreased enzymatic activity from 250 kV/cm	0°C
multi-protein system (lysozyme, ovalbumin, ovotransferrin) ⁴²⁰	2.5 MV/m	2 μ s	100 Hz	200, 400, 600, 800 μ s	chromatography, SDS-PAGE, turbidimetry	turbidity measurement and SDS–PAGE shows that lysozyme could be the reason for aggregation in multiprotein system during PEF due to electrostatic interactions and disulfide bonds, chromatography does not indicate aggregates inside samples	$\leq 18^\circ\text{C}$
multi-protein system (diluted egg white) ⁴²¹	2.5 MV/m	2 μ s	100 Hz	200, 400, 600, 800 μ s	soluble protein content determination, particle size distribution, and Z-average size measurement, zeta potential, protein carbonyl content measurement, free sulfhydryl content determination, electrophoresis (native/SDS-PAGE)	soluble protein content decrease, Z-average particle size increases after 400 μ s, creating aggregates, no increase in protein carbonyl content, a slight increase in free sulfhydryl content, electrophoresis showed that lysozyme prone to precipitation with other protein components(ovalbumin, ovotransferrin)	$\leq 18^\circ\text{C}$
lysozyme, pepsin ⁴²²	3.5 MV/m	bipolar: positive 2 μ s, negative 2 μ s, gap 20 μ s	NR	100 – 1200 μ s (lys.) / 600 μ s (pep.)	CD, enzymatic activity assay, sorbitol effect	disruption of secondary structure (far-UV CD): lysozyme loss of α -helical structure and pepsin loss of β -sheet structure, unfolded tertiary structure (near-UV CD), sorbitol has a structural protective effect on both proteins against PEF, enzymatic activity decreasing with a longer exposition of PEF	$\leq 45^\circ\text{C}$
microtubules (MTs) ²⁵	40.9 MV/m	1 ps	1 kHz	up to 11 min exposure (i.e. N=660 000 pulses)	light and fluorescence microscopy	MTs disassembly	RT
microtubules (MTs) ²⁵	10 MV/m	2.9 ps	1.5 THz, pulse 1 kHz firing frequency	up to 11 min exposure (i.e. N=660 000 pulses)	light and fluorescence microscopy	MTs disassembly	RT
microtubules (MTs) ²⁵	3.7 MV/m	6.3 ps	0.5 THz, pulse 1 kHz firing frequency	up to 11 min exposure (i.e. N=660 000 pulses)	light and fluorescence microscopy	MTs disassembly	RT
MTs ⁴²³	0.1–0.2 MV/m	continuous harmonic wave	3.5, 20, 29 GHz	200 s exposure time	turbidimetry assay of MT polymerization kinetics	-	28–39°C

Continued on next page

Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
tubulin during polymerization ⁴²⁴	2.5 V/m	2 ms	10 Hz	10 min. during polymerization	negative stain electron microscopy	formation of parallel oriented arrays of MTs in the direction of the field	37°C
MTs ⁴²⁵	< 50 kV/m	NR	10 kHz - MHz (sinus)	NR	dark field microscopy	parallel arrays of microtubules are formed due to the dipole moment induced along the long axis of the microtubules	25-28°C
ovalbumin (OVA), BSA, OVA+BSA ⁴²⁶	2, 2.5, 3 and 3.5 MV/m	2 μs	200 Hz	400 μs	high-performance size exclusion chromatography, Native/SDS-PAGE, sulphhydryl groups analysis	protein aggregation of OVA caused by decreasing sulphhydryl groups (≤2.5 MV/m); no aggregation effect of BSA probably because less sulphhydryl groups; aggregation effect of OVA+BSA caused by disulfide bond between proteins (≤2.5MV/m)	≤ 30°C
ovalbumin + divalent metal ions (Ca ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺) ⁴²⁷	0 to 5 MV/m	40 μs	1 kHz	565, 1130, 1695, 2260 μs	Raman spectroscopy, FTIR, fluorescence spectroscopy, surface tension, surface hydrophobicity,	Surface hydrophobicity and surface tension showed an enhanced trend at first and then reduced with pulse time. The spectra showed at the beginning of the pulse treatment, some hydrophobic amino acid side chains tended to be exposed. As PEF processing continued, ovalbumin's side chain groups were more inclined to be more intermolecular. Different metal ion types and pulse treat times modified the protein structure of ovalbumin.	4°C
ovalbumin ± Ca ²⁺ ¹⁶¹	0 to 5 MV/m	15 μs	1 kHz	720 to 4320 μs	CD, TEM	PEF linearly unfolding of secondary structure with increasing pulse intensity or treatment time (loss α-helix and decrease β-sheets) and perturbation on the tertiary structure was more significant than that on the secondary structure. Synergetic effect PEF + Ca ²⁺ increases effect of unfolding of secondary structure + creating nanotubes followed by aggregation effect with increasing conductivity.	20 to 45°C
ovalbumin / egg white ³⁹⁹	2.7 – 3.3 MV/m	0.3 or 0.9 μs	1.1 Hz	50 – 400 pulses (exponential decay)	free sulphhydryl group content analysis by DTNB, UV-spectroscopy, Gelation effect of Egg white	probably reversible partial protein unfolding, not cause any visible aggregation, without changes in gelation properties of egg white	< 29°C
ovomucoid (IgG1 and IgE antibodies) ⁴²⁸	1, 2, 3 or 4 MV/m	NR (similar works from the related groups use 2μs)	2000 Hz	flow rate 3.2 mL/min (neither the chamber volume nor the residence time is provided)	SDS-PAGE, SEM, contact angle assay, CD, FTIR spectroscopy	PEF reduced the binding ability of IgG1 and IgE in OVM, no changes in primary structure, changes in secondary structure- α-helix and β-sheets decrease, PEF treatment induced the expansion of protein molecules, and increased intermolecular forces in solution, surface hydrophobicity increased, Total-SH content decreased, SEM showed changes in microstructure of OVM (rod-shaped and spherical shape was transformed into irregular flake structure structures under the influence of PEF)	25°C
pea protein isolate ¹²⁶	0, 0.5–2.5 MV/m	40 μs (monopolar square wave)	1 kHz	20 (calculated from effective treatment time 0.8 ms)	enzymatic activity assay, FTIR, CD, TRP/TYR fluorescence, UV-absorption, SDS-PAGE	secondary structure, tertiary structure, unfolding, increased antioxidant capacity	<30°C
papain ²⁴⁷	2 – 5 MV/m	4 μs	0.8 or 2 ms	200 or 500 pulses	far UV CD, determination of papain activity and free cysteine content, reducing agent prevent oxidation	significant reduction of activity after 24 hours, decrease of free cysteine content after 24 hours, no change of pH after PEF, major inactivation effect of papain was related to the conformational change of α - helix, irreversibly inactivated	10°C
papain ⁴²⁹	1 and 1.3 MV/m	NR	0.2 Hz	48-432 pulses, (flow rate 0.2, 0.4, 6.6 L/min, chamber volume 0.13 mL estimated from electrodes dimensions)	residual activity, Relative protein concentration, sulphhydryl group content, Fluorescence spectrophotometer	enzymatic activity reduction, RPC and SH content decrease with the number of pulses for 0.2 and 0.4 L/min means secondary changes in structure, no significant changes in the ANS fluorescence - same surface hydrophobicity, higher peaks of fluorescence intensity for PEF means tertiary changes in structure, no emission shifts in wavelength	20°C (max 50°C measured)
pectinase ⁴³⁰	0.3 - 2.1 MV/m (square monopolar pulses)	5 – 20 μs	1 – 10 kHz	80 pulses, 50-160 mL/min (chamber volume NR)	enzyme kinetics, far UV CD, fluorescence spectroscopy, SDS-PAGE	pectinase activity increased with field strength (maximum at 12 kV/cm) and flow rate (maximum 80mL/min), PEF did not modify polypeptide chain composition according to SDS-PAGE, in the secondary structure of PEF sample α-helix and β-sheets increased and random coil content decrease, an increasing number of Trp residues on the surface of the pectinase molecules shows on changes in tertiary structure, PEF increased the thermal stability of pectinase	RT

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Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
horseradish peroxidase (POD), polyphenol oxidase (PPO) ⁴³¹	0.5–2.5 MV/m	POD: 1.4 and PPO: 0.6 μ s	10 Hz	POD: 290 – 1740 μ s, PPO: 124 – 744 μ s	enzyme activity assay, CD	enzymatic activity (decreased); secondary structure (decrease of α -helix content)	$\leq 40^\circ\text{C}$
pepsin ¹⁶²	1.78–3.29 MV/m	bipolar square pulses: 2 μ s positive, 18 μ s gap, 2 μ s negative	800 Hz	total treatment time 126–630 μ s, i.e. N=63 – 315 pulses	enzymatic activity, UV absorption, CD, solubility analysis	enzymatic activity deactivation, secondary structure loss, aggregation	$<52^\circ\text{C}$, pepsin claimed to be stable $<60^\circ\text{C}$,
horseradish peroxidase, β -galactosidase, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), glucoamylase, enolase, invertase ⁴³²	0.4 – 2.3 MV/m	2 μ s	50 Hz	30 or 60 s	enzyme activity assay, SDS-PAGE	enzymatic activity (increased with lower and decreased with higher EF strength); the degree of the influence by PEF treatment seemed to be greatly different by the type of enzyme; refolding enhancement of the thermal denatured peroxidase	NR
the second PDZ domain of the human E3 ubiquitin ligase LNX2 (LNX2) ^{PDZ2 22}	~ 50 –100 MV/m	50–500 ns	- (effects observed within single pulse)	-	X-ray crystallography	the symmetry of the protein crystal was reduced; perturbations of nearly every type of physical interaction throughout the protein structure—induction of side-chain rotamer flips, continuous displacement of backbone atoms, side chains and bound waters, propagated rotamer shifts suggesting collective motions through the structure, breaking and re-forming of hydrogen bonds, global motions of entire secondary structure elements, and complex coordinated changes in large regions	RT
plasmin (fibrinolysis) ²⁴⁸	0, 1.5 - 4.5 MV/m	2 μ s	0.1 Hz	10–50 pulses	enzymatic activity assay	enzymatic activity (decreased)	10–15 $^\circ\text{C}$
polyphenol oxidase (PPO) ⁴³³	1 MV/m / 0.9 MV/m	-	AC voltage, capacitively coupled: 10 Hz to 760 kHz	0 – 6 min	enzyme activity assay	frequency-dependent inhibition or stimulation of PPO enzyme activity	NR, remained constant
protamex (bacillolysins and subtilisin) ²⁵¹	1.4 and 1.82 MV/m	20 μ s	10 Hz	0 – 900 pulses	enzymatic activity assay	inactivation of the enzyme	18 to 55 $^\circ\text{C}$
protease (from <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>) ⁴³⁴	0.62 MV/m	700 μ s	0.1 Hz	0, 10 and 20 pulses	enzymatic activity assay	inhibition of the enzymatic activity	15 to 20 $^\circ\text{C}$
S-adenosylhomocysteinyl (AdoHcy), 5'-methylthadenosine (MTA) ²⁵⁰	325 – 583 V/m (calculated from 1.5–3.1 W/g, assuming water as the material)	-	10.4 GHz continuous irradiation	0 – 90 min	enzymatic activity assays, CD spectroscopy	irreversible time- and temperature -dependent inactivation of both enzymes	70 to 90 $^\circ\text{C}$ (below the denaturation temperature of the given enzymes)
soy protein isolate ¹⁸⁰	0.5–3 MV/m	pulse pair: 40 μ s, 40 μ s 200 gap, μ s opposite polarity	1 kHz	51 (calculated from flow, volumes, total treatment time)	turbidimetry, DLS, SDS-PAGE, size exclusion chromatography, carbonyl content (DNPH), sulfhydryl content (DTNB), surface hydrophobicity (ANS), CD, TRP/TYR fluorescence	secondary structure, tertiary structure, protein-protein interaction, aggregation	20 to 30 $^\circ\text{C}$
spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 ²⁹⁰	<5 kV/m (estimated based on 700 W and geometry of the waveguide)	-	2.45 GHz microwave	2, 5 and 10 min.	UV-spectroscopy	Significant denaturation can be induced by microwave irradiation	37 $^\circ\text{C}$
Sup35NM (prion) ²³⁸	1, 2 MV/m	50, 1000 μ s	1 Hz	10 pulses	AFM	Significant reductions in the length of prion fibrils, full disintegration of fibrils	RT (NR) + rise $<4.6^\circ\text{C}$

Continued on next page

Protein [Reference]	Field strength	Pulse width / duration	Frequency	Exposure	Techniques used	Effects observed	Temp.
trans-thyretin aggregates ²²⁶	126 MV/m	1 ns	1.7 Hz	0, 200–1000 pulses	native/SDS-PAGE, BCA method, fluorescence microscopy	protein aggregates disassembly	23°C
tropomyosin ¹³⁴	0.5–2 MV/m	10 μs	5 Hz	up to 4500 pulses (calculated from flow, volumes, total treatment time)	DLS, CD, PAGE, FTIR, TRP/TYR fluorescence, carbonyl content (DNPH), surface hydrophobicity (ANS)	secondary structure, tertiary structure, interactions (depolymerization (from dimers), antibody binding)	N.D. / ice water bath
tubulin ²¹	2 MV/m	11 ns	1 Hz	0 – 800 pulses	intrinsic (TRP, TYR) fluorescence, dynamic light scattering, zeta potential, atomic force microscopy, 2D-PAGE and immunoblotting	protein conformation, hydrodynamic radius, effective charge, capability of self-assembly	25°C
tubulin, microtubules ⁸⁰	100 to 400 kV/m	25 to 300 μs	1	effects are observed within N=1 pulse	Electric birefringence method	tubulin and microtubule orientation, affected by microtubule-associated proteins	10–20°C
ubiquitin (Ub) ¹⁶³	18 and 90 mW/cm ² (E=260, 582 V/m)	0.8 μs	95 GHz radiation, 10 kHz pulse firing rate	0 – 12 min total exposure, i.e. 5.76 s net exposure	NMR	change of rate hydrogen-deuterium exchange of the protein amides (accelerated in the protein interior and in hydrophobic surfaces while decelerated in the surface loop and short 3 ₁₀ helix regions)	25°C
whey protein isolate ³⁵⁵	1.5 and 3 MV/m	25 μs	1.04 kHz	7.35 ms (N=294 pulses)	SDS-PAGE, far-UV CD spectroscopy, measurement of free amino groups (o-phthalaldehyde (OPA) method)	EF promoted glycosylation of protein -> decreased content of secondary structure and free amino groups, increase of glycosylation and emulsion stability	30±0.5°C

Table 3 Effects of electric field on proteins observed in molecular dynamics simulations

System of study [Reference]	Type, shape of field	Field strength	Force field and water type (where available)	Condition of simulation	Simulation length	Observable
act d 2 kiwi fruit allergen ⁴³⁵	E, oscillating (2450 MHz)	50 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (300, 325, 350, 375 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	2 ns	secondary structure, RMSD, RMSF, SASA
alanine polypeptide ¹⁸⁵	E static	50-1000 MV/m	OPLS/AA, no water	NA	400 ns	secondary structure, entropy, enthalpy
alcalase ²⁴⁴	E, static	1 MV/m	CHARMM36	NA	200 ns	RMSD, H-bond, SASA, radius of gyration
amyloid- β peptide ¹⁵¹	E, static	20 MV/m	amber99SB-ILDN, TIP3P	NPT (310 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	200 ns	secondary structure
amyloid- β ¹⁴⁷	E, static	200-500 MV/m	Amber ff99SB-ILDN, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	20 ns	dipole moment
amyloid- β peptide ¹⁷⁴	E, oscillating (1 GHz)	10, 100, 200 MV/m	NVT (300 K)	CHARMM36m	300 ns	RMSD, RMSF, h-bond, secondary structure, free energy
A β -42 Peptide ¹³³	E, static, Oscillating (0.1-1 GHz)	175, 200 MV/m	ff14SB, TIP3P	NVT(300 K, Monte Carlo)	100 ns	interpeptide distance, radius of gyration, dispersion entropy, dipole moment, potential of mean force
β -amyloid (1BA4) ²¹⁴	E, static	100, 250, 500, 1000 MV/m	CHARMM, TIP3P	NPT	10 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration
β -amyloid ¹⁷⁵	E, static, oscillating (0.1, 1 GHz)	100, 200 MV/m,	ff14SB, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Langevin thermostat, Berendsen barostat)	500 ns	RMSD, H-bonds, dipole moment, secondary structure
apoC-II peptide ⁴³⁶	E, EM, static, oscillating (1000, 2500 and 5000 MHz)	0.7 to 700 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (300K, Berendsen)	200ns	radius of gyration (Rg), N-C termini distance, dipole moment, radial distribution functions (rdf), hydrogen bonding
apoC-II peptide ¹⁵³	E, EM, static	7kV/m to 700MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (300K, Berendsen)	4.8 μ s	RMSD, dipole moment, free energy map, Radius of gyration, amino acids conformations
ara h 6 peanut protein ¹⁵⁵	E static, oscillating (2450 MHz)	50 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (Berendsen, 300, 380, 425 K)	1 ns	RMSD, radius of gyration, dipole moment, SASA, secondary structure
aquaglyceroporin-7 ⁴³⁷	E static, oscillating (10 GHz)	0.2 MV/m	CHARMM36, SPC/E	NPT (300 K, Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	70 ns	RMSD, RMSF, radius of gyration, free energy, H-bonds, water permeation
Human Aquaporin 4 ¹⁸⁸	E static, oscillating (2.45, 20, 50, 100, 200 MHz)	65 MV/m to 25 GV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (298 K, Nosé-Hoover, Langevin dynamics)	9 μ s	open and closed states of selectivity filter, dipole, potential-of-mean-force profile
bovine insulin (2A3G) ¹⁵⁷	E, static	150-600 MV/m	Amber03, TIP3P	NPT (Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	1 μ s	dipole moment, secondary structure, H-bonds
BSA, trypsin ¹⁵⁸	E, static	0.03-10000 MV/m	AMBER all-atom, TIP3P	NA	NA	RMSD
BSA ²⁴⁰	E, static	1.2 MV/m	OPLS-AA, TIP3P	NPT	30 ns	SASA, secondary structure
carnosine ¹⁹¹	EM, oscillating (2.45 GHz)	$10^{-6} - 10^2$ V/m	OPLS-AA	NVT (velocity rescaling)	20 ns	electrostatic potential surface, dipole moment, molecular collision number, kinetic energy of collision
β -casein (BCN) ¹⁶⁰	E, sinusoidal	4-4000 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT(300 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	10 ns	RMSD, RMSF, radius of gyration, dipole moment, secondary structure, distance matrix for residue pairs, SASA
Cav2.1 channel ¹⁸³	E, oscillating (40.12, 42.5, 42.65, 42.83, 46.63, 48.5 THz)	600 MV/m	CHARMM36, POPC, TIP3P	NPT (315 K, Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	3 ns	free energy profile, H-bonds, vibrational spectra
chignolin (1UAO) ⁴³⁸	E, static	100, 250, 500 and 1000 MV/m	CHARMM27 and TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Berendsen thermostat)	10 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration

Continued on next page

System of study [Reference]	Type, shape of field	Field strength	Force field and water type (where available)	Condition of simulation	Simulation length	Observable
chignolin ⁴³⁹	E static oscillating (9-3600 ps period, i.e.)	1000 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Berendsen)	10 ns	RMSD, secondary structure, dipole moment
chignolin ¹⁸¹	E static oscillating (2.45 GHz)	200 MV/m	AMBER99SB, TIP4P/2005	NPT (300 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	5 μ s	RMSD, SASA, free energy, hydrogen bonds, Ramachandran plot analysis
connexin 26 hemichannel (2ZW3) ¹⁵²	E, static, oscillating (2.4 and 50 GHz)	100, 175, 250, 325, 400 MV/m	CHARMM 36, TIP3	NPT (310 K, Nosé Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	50 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, H-bonds, tertiary structure
Cytochrome c ¹⁵⁴	E, static	500-2000 MV/m	CHARMM, TIP3P	NVT (310 K, Berendsen)	40 ns	protein-surface distance, protein orientation, radial distribution function, protein-surface interaction energy, RMSD
dihydro-lipoamide dehydrogenase (1BBL) ¹⁴⁹	E, static	200-800 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (310 K)	30 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration, H-bonds
diphenyl-alanine peptide ¹⁴⁴	E, static	13 GV/m, 19.5 GV/m	CHARMM 36-AA, TIP3P, REMD	NPT (Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	98 to 126 ns	potential energy, RMSD, dipole moment
dronpa ³⁴⁸	E, static	0.4-1.3 GV/m	CHARMM27, water model not mentioned?	Langevin dynamics, 300K	85 ps	dipole moment
ferritin ¹⁴¹	E, static	1 MV/m	CHARMM36	NA	350 ns	RMSD, SASA
fibronectin-hydroxyapatite ¹⁴⁶	E, static	250-1000 MV/m	AMBER99SB ILDN, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	100 ns	protein-ligand contacts, interaction energy, dipole moment, solvent radial distribution function
hemoglobin ⁴⁴⁰	E, linear/circularly polarized (5.9 GHz)	10, 7.1 V/m (looks like a typo, maybe authors meant GV/m)	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT (310 K)	50 ns	RMSD, secondary structure
HEWL ²¹³	E/M, oscillating (50-500 GHz)	1-5 GV/m (RMS)	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NVT (300 K, Nosé Hoover)	1 ns	RMSD, dipole moment
HEWL mutants ⁴⁴¹	E/M, static, oscillating (2.45GHz)	100 to 1500 MV/m (RMS for osc, and ampl for static)	GROMOS96 and SPC	NPT (Noose-Hoover)	2.5-25 ns	RMSD, dipole moment
HEWL mutant (2LZT) ⁴⁰¹	E/M, oscillating (2.45-100 GHz)	500 MV/m (RMS)	GROMOS96, SPC	NPT (300 K)	5 ns	H-bond
HEWL ¹⁸⁶	E, static, oscillating (2.45, 10, and 100 GHz)	50, 100, 200 MV/m	AMBER99SB, TIP4P/2005	NPT (v-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	100 ns	water density distribution, dipole moment
human Aquaporin 4 ¹⁸⁷	E, static, oscillating (2.45, 100 GHz)	65 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (298 K, Nosé-Hoover, Langevin dynamics)	50 ns	dipole moment
human aquaporin 4 (3GD8) in lipid bilayer ⁴⁴²	E, oscillating circularly polarized (100 GHz)	500 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (298 K)	60 ns	pore radius, mean square displacement (MSD) of water
human aquaporin 4 ²⁶³	E, static	200-500 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (298 K, Nosé-Hoover chains, Langevin dynamics piston)	2-11 ns	ion conductivity, pore radius profile
insulin chain-B (1ZNI) ⁴⁴³	E, static, oscillating (2.45 GHz)	10-1000 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, 400 K, Nosé-Hoover)	1.7-10 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure
insulin chain-B (1ZNI) ⁴⁴⁴	E, oscillating (1.225, 4.9 GHz)	10 to 500 MV/m (Amplitude)	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Nosé-Hoover)	10 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration
integrins ⁴⁴⁵	E, static, oscillating (PEF)	0.0015, 0.015, 0.15 MV/m for static; 0.3, 1, 3 MV/m for pulse (pulse width 10, 100, 1000 μ s)	Monte Carlo simulations	NA	20 s	integrin clustering
kinesin-tubulin ²²⁵	E, static	30-100 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NVT (300 K, Nosé-Hoover)	30 ns	RMSD, intermolecular contacts, dipole moment, translational/rotational work, secondary structure

Continued on next page

System of study [Reference]	Type, shape of field	Field strength	Force field and water type (where available)	Condition of simulation	Simulation length	Observable
laccase ⁴⁴⁶	E, static	0.01-1000 MV/m	OPLS/AA, SPC	NPT (300 K)	50 ns	RMSD, h-bonds, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration, binding affinity
β -lactoglobulin ⁴⁴⁷	E, Oscillating (2.45 GHz)	0.5 GV/m	Amber 99SB—ILDN	NPT (300, 333, 348, 363 K)	2 ns	secondary structure, RMSD, RMSF, radius of gyration, dipole moment, SASA
β -lactoglobulin ¹⁴⁸	E, static	3000 MV/m	Amberff14SB, TIP3P	NVT (300, 400, 450 K, Berendsen, Langevin dynamics)	240 ns	RMSD, RMSF, SASA, dipole moment
L-type calcium channel ⁴⁴⁸	E, static, oscillating (1, 2.5 GHz)	30 MV/m	GROMOS 96-43a1, SPC	NPT (310 K, Nosé-Hoover, Berendsen)	10ns	RMSD, RMSF, H-bonds
lysozyme, myoglobin ¹⁵⁶	E, static	424 MV/m	Amber99SB, TIP3P	NVT (Langevin dynamics, 298 K)	40 ns	dipole moment, SASA
Model peptides ⁴⁰⁰	E, static	1, 5 GV/m	DFT/PCM, water, ethanol			free energy, conformational stability, secondary structure, hydrogen bonds
myofibrillar proteins ¹⁴⁵	E, static	0.8-2.8 V/m	Gromacs 53a6, SPC	NPT (277 K, Berendsen thermostat and barostat)	30 ns	H-bonds, radius of gyration
Myoglobin ¹⁹⁰	EM, oscillating (1 GHz)	0.001 to 500 MV/m	perturbed matrix method	NPT (300 K)	10-20 ns	RMSD, free energy
myoglobin ¹⁵⁹	E, static, pulse	100-1000 MV/m	GROMOS43a1, SPC	NVT (Berendsen)	100ns	dipole moment, secondary structure
myoglobin ⁴⁴⁹	E, gaussian pulse (time length=8 ns), bipolar pulse (time length=2 ns)	100-1000 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NVT (300 K, Berendsen)	20 ns	dipole moment, sec str, H-bonds
myoglobin ²²¹	E, static	100 V/m to 1000 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NVT (300 K)	100 ns	dipole moment, secondary structure
Myoglobin ²²⁰	E, Oscillating (0.1-100 GHz)	2-200 MV/m	ffG43a1, SPC	NVT (200 K, Berendsen thermostat)	50 ns	dipole moment
voltage-gated ion channels: NavMs, NavPaS, HCN1 ²⁶⁶	E, static, pulse	97-108 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NVT(300 K, Nosé-Hoover)	200 ns	secondary structure, pore size, salt-bridge, ion conduction
ovalbumin ¹⁴⁰	E, static, oscillating (2.5 GHz)	500 MV/m	CHARMM33, TIP3P	NPT (300, 320, 340, 360 K, Nosé-Hoover)	5 ns	secondary structure, Hydrogen bonds, saltbridge interactions, radius of gyration, dipole moment, SASA
peptides ⁴⁵⁰	E, static	1.2-5 GV/m	DFT/PCM, vacuum			free energy, geometry of the metal complex, dipole moment
α -helix peptides ⁶⁸	E, Pulsed, Oscillating (1-2 GHz)	500 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3	NPT (310 K)	10 ns	RMSD, RMSF, dipole moment, secondary structure
β -sheet peptides ¹⁸⁴	E, static	4, 6, 10 GV/m	PARAM27, TIP3P	NVE (300 K)	4 ns	potential of mean force (PMF)
pancreatic trypsin inhibitor (BPTI) ³⁴⁷	E, static, square wave[pulse], oscillating	100 MV/m, 2 GV/m and 2.17 GV/m	CHARMM	NVE (100 K)	150 ps	RMSD, dipole moment
pea protein isolate ¹²⁶	E, static	1 MV/m	OPLS-AA, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	25 ns	RMSD, RMSF, SASA, secondary structure
pectin methylesterase ¹⁴²	E, static	0.007-1000 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (323 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Rahman)	5 ns	RMSF, RMSD, radius of gyration, SASA, B-factor, water dynamics, hydration of enzyme, intra/inter-molecular H-bonds, dipole moment, Ramachandran plots
pentamer AB(17-42) (2BEG) ²³⁴	E, static	250, 500 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT(300 K, Berendsen, Langevin dynamics)	50 ns	RMSD, secondary structure, radius of gyration, H-bonds
polygalacturonase ⁴⁵¹	E, static	0.75 - 1.25 GV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT	10 ns	secondary structure, RMSD, RMSF, H-bonds, hydrophobic SASA, dipole moment, free binding energy
soybean Hydrophobic Protein ⁴⁵²	E, static	2, 4, 3000 MV/m	CHARMM27, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Berendsen)	1 ns	RMSD, dipole moment, secondary structure, radius of gyration, SASA

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System of study [Reference]	Type, shape of field	Field strength	Force field and water type (where available)	Condition of simulation	Simulation length	Observable
SARS-CoV-2 spike protein ¹²⁵	E, static	0.1-10 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Nosé Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	700 ns	RMSD, RMSF, secondary structure
SARS-CoV-2 spike protein ¹³⁹	E, static	0.1-100 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Nosé Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	700 ns	RMSD, RMSF, secondary structure, free energy, electrostatic potential
addlinespace serotonin 1A receptor (5-HT1AR) ¹³⁵	E, static	10-30 MV/m	AMBER 14SB, TIP3P	NPT (310 K, Nosé Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	600 ns	RMSD, radius of gyration, contact number between protein and ligand, dipole moment.
serotonin 1A receptor (5-HT1AR) ¹³⁷	E, static	20 MV/m	AMBER 14SB, TIP3P	NPT (310 K, velocity-rescaling, Parrinello-Rahman)	500 ns	RMSD, h-bond, residue contact count, dipole moment, secondary structure
SOD1 ²¹⁶	E, Monopolar, bipolar nsPEF (pulse duration 2ns)	100-700 MV/m	GROMOS96, SPC	NVT(300 K, V-rescale)	200 ns	dipole moment, secondary structure, RMSD, SASA, Radius of gyration
soybean beta-conglycinin, Soybean glycinin ¹⁸⁰	E, static	100, 200, 300 MV/m	Gromos 53a6, TIP3P	NPT(300 K)	30 ns	RMSD, H-bonds, secondary structure
amyloid-beta fibrils ¹³⁶	E, static, oscillating (0.2 GHz)	200-400 MV/m	AMBER99SB-ILDN, TIP3P	NPT (310 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	500 ns	secondary structure, dipole moment, dielectric constant, H-bonds, PCA
thioredoxin ¹⁸²	E, static	20-120 MV/m	SPC	NPT (300-350 K)	100 ns	pKa, free energy, PCA, SASA, H-bonds, dipole moment
tropomyosin ¹³⁴	E, static	0.5, 1.0, 2.0 MV/m	CHARMM36, SPC/E	NPT(298.15 K)	50 ns	secondary structure, H-bonds, SASA
tubulin ²¹⁸	E, static, oscillating (1, 10 GHz)	30 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (300 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	500 ps	Elastic constant, Young's modulus
tubulin ¹⁵⁰	E, static	5-75 MV/m	CHARMM36	NPT(310 K, Langevin dynamics, Nosé-Hoover-Langevin)	10 ns	RMSD, RMSF, dipole moment
tubulin, kinesin ²³³	E, oscillating (1–10 GHz)	30 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (310 K, Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	10 ns	Flexibility of Mts, kinesin affinity to tubulin
tubulin-kinesin complex ²¹⁷	E, static	100 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NVT (Nosé-Hoover thermostat)	100 ns	dipole moment, RMSF, contact surface
tubulin ⁷⁸	E, static	10 to 300 MV/m	amber03 force field, TIP3P	NVT (300 K)	30 ns	dipole moment, sec str, shape and orientation (rotation) of protein
tubulin ring ⁴⁶	E, static	50, 100 MV/m	Amberff14SB, TIP3P	NPT (Langevin thermostat, 0.5 ps coupling)	50 ns	dipole moment, binding energy
$\alpha\beta$ -tubulin and kinesin ²³²	E, Oscillating(1 to 10 GHz)	30 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (310 K, Parrinello-Rahman)	500 ps	kinesin affinity to tubulin dimer
$\alpha\beta$ -tubulin dimer ²¹⁹	E, Oscillating (1-10 GHz)	30 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (310 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)	300 ps	elastic constant
$\alpha\beta$ -tubulin ⁴⁵³	E, Oscillating (900 MHz, 2450 MHz)	10 MV/m	GROMOS96-43a1, SPC	NPT (310 K, Nosé Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	1 ns	RMSD, elastic constant, young modulus
Trp-cage, Ctf, ubiquitin, lysozyme ⁷⁹	E, static	0 to 3 GV/m	OPLS-AA/L, vacuum	no-PBC (300 K, Berendsen)	10-50 ns	RMSD, degree of orientation, total internal energy
ubiquitin ¹²³	E, time dependent	100 to 3000 MV/m	OPLS-AA, vaccume	NVT (300 K, Berendsen thermostat)	5 to 14 ns	degree of orientation, RMSD
ubiquitin ⁴⁷	E, static	3000 MV/m to 11000 MV/m	OPLS/AA	NVT (300 K, Berendsen thermostat)	50 ps	Unfolding, RMSD
ubiquitin ¹³⁸	E, static	10-200 MV/m	amber99sb-ildn, SPC/E	1 μ s	NPT (310 K, Berendsen, Parrinello-Ra	RMSD, RMSF, h-bonds, dipole moment, radius of gyration
ubiquitin ⁸²	E, static	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT(300 K, Langevin dynamics, Nosé-Hoover)			dipole moment, SASA, RMSD, radius of gyration, protein rotational diffusion, water diffusion
ubiquitin ¹³⁰	E, static	0.05-3.0 GV/m	OPLS-AA, TIP4P	no-PBC(300 K, Berendsen)	10 ns	dipole orientation, dipole moment, RMSF, RMSD, diffraction pattern

Continued on next page

System of study [Reference]	Type, shape of field	Field strength	Force field and water type (where available)	Condition of simulation	Simulation length	Observable
voltage sensing domain (VSD) of the Nav1.5 sodium cardiac channel ⁴⁵⁴	E, static	100-200 MV/m	CHARMM36, POPC	NPT(310 K, Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	50 ns	RMSD, clustering structures, density profile of clusters based on RMSD and FNC (fraction of native contacts), free energy
voltage-gated potassium (Kv) channel ⁴⁵⁵	E, static	40 MV/m	CHARMM22, TIP3P	NPT (300 K, Langevin dynamics, Langevin piston)	20 ns	secondary structure, RMSD, water density, pore-radius profile
voltage-gated potassium (Kv4) channel ⁴⁵⁶	E, static	250 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT(310 K,Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	4 ns	pore radius, cross-sectional area, dipole moment
voltage-gated potassium (Kv1.2) channel ⁴⁵⁷	E, Oscillating (36.75 37.06, 37.68, and 38.2 THz)	400 MV/m	CHARMM36m, CHARMM TIP3P	NPT (310 K, V-rescale, Parrinello-Rahman)		dihedral angle, ion permeation, RMSD, RMSF, potassium ion occupancy
voltage-gated Ca ²⁺ channel ¹⁴³	E, static	100, 200 MV/m	CHARMM36, TIP3P	NPT (310 K,Nosé-Hoover, Parrinello-Rahman)	50 ns	RMSD,fraction of native contacts (FNC), free energy

Table 4 List of abbreviations.

Abbrev.	Full text	Abbrev.	Full text
A β	amyloid-beta	MTA	5'-methylthioadenosine
AC	alternating current	NEMD	non-equilibrium molecular dynamics
AQP	aquaporin	NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
AdoHcy	S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine	nsPEF	nanosecond pulsed electric field
AFM	atomic force microscopy	OPA	o-phthalaldehyde
ANS	L-anilinonaphthalene-8-sulphonate	OVA	ovalbumin
anti-DNP	antidinitrophenyl	PCA	principal component analysis
AP	alkaline phosphatase	PDB	Protein Data Bank
ATR-FTIR	attenuated total reflectance Fourier-transform IR	PDMS	poly(dimethylsiloxane)
BCA	bicinchoninic-acid protein assay	PEF	pulsed electric field
BSA	bovine serum albumin	POD	peroxidase
CD	circular dichroism	PPI	protein-protein interaction
CLSM	confocal laser scanning microscopy	PPO	polyphenol oxidase
CW	continuous wave	PL	photoluminescence
DC	direct current	PMF	potential of mean force
DFT	density functional theory	R _g	radius of gyration
DLS	dynamic light scattering	RMSD	root-mean-square deviation
DNP	2,4-dinitrophenyl-hydrazine (carbonyl assay)	RMSF	root-mean-square fluctuation
DSC	differential scanning calorimetry	ROA	Raman optical activity
DTNB	5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid)	ROS	reactive oxygen species
EF	electric field	RNS	reactive nitrogen species
EGFP	enhanced green fluorescent protein	RPC	relative protein concentration
EM	electromagnetic	RXS	reactive species (generic)
EMC	expand-maximize-compress	SASA	solvent-accessible surface area
EWOD	electrowetting-on-dielectric	SAXS	small-angle X-ray scattering
FNC	fraction of native contacts	SEC	size-exclusion chromatography
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared	SEM	scanning electron microscopy
GFP	green fluorescent protein	SDS-PAGE	sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
GFPuv5	ultraviolet-excitable GFP variant (uv5)	SiR	silicon-rhodamine (fluorophore)
GPCR	G-protein-coupled receptor	SPI	single-particle imaging
H-bond	hydrogen bond	SPR	surface plasmon resonance
HEWL	hen egg-white lysozyme	TEM	transmission electron microscopy
HPLC	high-performance liquid chromatography	ThT	thioflavin T
HRTEM	high-resolution transmission EM	Trp	tryptophan
HRP	horseradish peroxidase	Tyr	tyrosine
HSA	human serum albumin	Ub	ubiquitin
HPG	high-power generator	UV-vis	ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy
HV	high voltage	VCD	vibrational circular dichroism
ITO	indium tin oxide	VG	voltage generator
LDH	lactate dehydrogenase	VGIC	voltage-gated ion channel
LLPS	liquid-liquid phase separation	VSD	voltage-sensing domain
MD	molecular dynamics	XFEL	X-ray free-electron laser
Mb	myoglobin	β -lg	β -lactoglobulin
MT	microtubule		